

D1.2 Operational Demo Cases

NextGen
December 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N°776541

Technical references

Project Acronym: NextGen

Project Title: Towards the next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy

Deliverable: D1.2 Operational demo cases

Dissemination level: Public

Type: Demonstrator

Work Package: WP1

Lead beneficiary: EURECAT

Contributing beneficiaries: KWB, UBATH

Submission date: 15-12-2020 (M30)

Disclaimer: Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency and the European Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Executive Summary

Work package 1 (WP1) of the NextGen project aims to demonstrate the feasibility of innovative technological solutions towards a circular economy (CE) in the water sector. With the goal of closing water, energy and materials cycles, several CE technologies have been implemented in 10 demo cases in order to collect long-term data on system performances to assess their benefits and drawbacks.

This deliverable **demonstrates the operational status of 10 demo cases deployed in 8 EU Member States and their specific NextGen objectives and CE solutions.** For each demo case, the deliverable show pictures of the prototypes and pilots installed, introduces the first technical results obtained until M30, provides the specific KPIs (actual and expected) and the expected next steps per each site.

A general introduction to the 10 demo cases can be found in the factsheets uploaded to the project website: <https://nextgenwater.eu/demonstration-cases>. All sites have started their demonstration activities and have shown their operability in M30 with the exception of the demo case of Timisoara (RO) which was incorporated in M19 replacing Bucharest. For Timisoara case, a detailed next step plan is provided as activities are being deployed at the moment.

Executive summary

Site	Status	Page
1. Braunschweig (DE)	Start-up of full scale operation of a TPH to increase biogas production. Nutrient recovery at full scale.	8
2. Costa Brava (SP)	Pilot plant in operation with regenerated membranes	33
3. Westland (NL)	Regional water balance done. HT-ATES at Koppert-Cress: installed with monitoring system	57
4. Alternheim (CH)	Evaluation of produced GAC under long-term tests at pilot scale. PK fertilizer pilot plant and NH4 stripping full-scale evaluation ready to start	90
5. Sernal (UK)	AnMBR under construction at R2IC and plant in use forecast for Jan 2021	116
6. La Trappe (NL)	MNR in operation. Protein production in Bio-Makeries start in December 2020.	138
7. Gotland (SE)	Wells installed for rainwater collection and IoT set-up. Installation automatic hatche at lake outflow pending and selection of site for infiltration on-going. Pilot for membrane treatment under construction.	169
8. Athens (GR)	MBR pilot plant for sewer mining in operation.	198
9. Filton (UK)	Rain water harvesting installed and availability defined. Desk studies on energy and material recovery.	217
10. Timisoara (RO)	Site to start their thermochemical sludge conversion demonstration activities in early 2021. Desk study on the feasibility of water reuse on-going.	243

Introduction

D1.1 described the **baseline conditions** of each of the demo cases involved in NextGen before the start of the project and all pre-existing infrastructures and systems – prior to NextGen interventions across water, energy and material cycles

D1.2 shows the **operation of new CE solutions** proposed by the project, at each demo case

The benefits and improvements achieved within the NextGen project at each demo case, will be reported in D1.3, D1.4, D1.5 (on the technical performance of the solutions related to the water, energy, materials cycles), D1.6, D1.7 (technology evidence data base), and D1.8 (greenfield implementation)

The economic and environmental performance of the CE solutions will be assessed in WP2

Objective

D1.2 objective is to provide evidence that the NextGen solutions at the demo cases are operational

Current operational status of each site is demonstrated by providing pictures/videos of the implemented NextGen solutions as well as first technical results obtained until M30

Table of contents for each demo case

1. General description of the site
2. State of play at the start of NextGen
3. Objectives of NextGen solutions applied in the case
 - Infographic: positioning of demo case within the CE
4. Summary table
 - Technology baseline, NextGen intervention, TRL, capacity, quantified target, status of the actions
5. NextGen solutions
 - Scheme characteristics, pictures/video of operation
6. Operational procedures
 - Pilot plant operation, economic and environmental assessment tools
7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions (actual vs expected)
8. Progress and next steps planned

#1. Braunschweig

Germany

Circular solutions for

Materials

Energy

Relevant data

WWTP (actual load: 350,000 PE)

Relevant sectors

Water treatment

Agriculture

Energy

Lead partner:

Other partner:

KOMPETENZZENTRUM
Wasser Berlin

Introduction to the demo case: <https://nextgenwater.eu/braunschweig/>

1. General description of the site

WWTP in Braunschweig (actual load: 350,000 PE)

- **Primary treatment:** bar screens, sand trap, primary clarifier
- **Secondary treatment:** nitrification, denitrification, enhanced biological phosphorus removal, secondary clarifier
- **Water Reuse:** irrigation of agricultural areas
- **Sludge treatment & reuse:** anaerobic digestion & direct reuse in agriculture (60%) and incineration (40%)

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Sludge treatment, direct reuse of digestate in agriculture (60%) and incineration of dewatered digestate (40%) until 2019

Primary sludge, FOG & excess sludge

Primary sludge, FOG & e: excess sludge

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Starting status of sludge treatment at the WWTP:

three full-scale one-stage digesters

NextGen solution implemented in the sludge treatment:

1. Two-stage digestion system
2. Thermal pressure hydrolysis (TPH) between the two stages
3. System for struvite precipitation
4. System for ammonium sulfate production

Benefits of thermal pressure hydrolysis:

- Higher availability of dissolved carbon compounds due to cell lysis
- Higher methane yield in second digestion stage
- Increase in dissolved phosphate and ammonium concentration

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Braunschweig

4. Summary Table: energy & material

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 1 Braunschweig (DE) Location: WWTP Braunschweig	Sub-Task 1.3.2 Internal heat usage and heat management for two-stage digestion system & TPH	Three one-stage digesters; heat reuse from CHPs for tempering the digesters and the surrounding buildings	Two-stage digestion system with thermal pressure hydrolysis (TPH) between the two stages: higher heat demand due to TPH, reuse of excess heat from TPH and more available heat from CHP due to increased methane yield	Digestion system with TPH: TRL 8 → 9	On average: up to 250 m ³ /h methane production without TPH; with TPH increase to 330 m ³ /h	Biogas production: Up to 25% increase in methane production due to TPH.	Due to unexpected and necessary retrofitting measures for the plant and due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant was stopped for 3 months. Since October 2020, the recovery plant is in operation again.
	Sub-Task 1.4.7 Full-scale nutrient recovery from wastewater	Irrigation and fertilization of agricultural fields with WWTP effluent and digestate	Phosphorus recovery for struvite production	TRL 9	Around 250 t struvite (dry)/year equals to 30 t P/year and 15 t N/year	Struvite precipitation (≥90% of P recovered from P load to recovery unit)	
			Ammonia stripping for ammonium sulfate production	TRL 9	Around 2200 t ammonium sulfate solution (wet)/year equals to 170 t N/year	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (>85% of N recovered from N load to recovery unit)	

5. NextGen solutions: nutrient and enhanced energy recovery since 2019

*Electricity is needed in each process step
(the demands are not indicated the scheme)

5.1 Pictures of the two-stage digestion system and TPH

1st stage: 1 digester

Thermal pressure hydrolysis (TPH)

T= 150 °C, p= 4.5 bar

2nd stage: 2 digesters

Important for nutrient recovery:

increase in ammonium and phosphate concentrations due to TPH

5.2 Flow scheme of struvite production

5.2 Pictures of struvite production unit & struvite

5.3 Flow scheme of ammonia stripping unit & $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ production

5.3 Pictures of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ production system

6. Operational procedures and methodologies

Main operation and analytical parameters

Biogas production incl. TPH:

Varying process parameters such as temperature in order to increase the methane yield

Struvite production:

Optimization of production process aiming at the increase in grain size and a high P recovery rate via changes in hydrocyclone geometry, different $MgCl_2$ dosages, varying HRT

Ammonium sulfate solution production:

Optimization of production process aiming at a high N recovery rate and low energy and chemicals consumption (→ varying temperature & NaOH addition)

6. Operational procedures and methodologies: Tools (WP2)

In the frame of WP2, different tools will be applied at the case study in Braunschweig:

- Quantitative chemical risk assessment for struvite and ammonium sulfate
- Life cycle assessment
- Life cycle costing
- Cost efficiency analysis

The results are elaborated in WP2 and will be presented in D2.1 and D2.2.

7.1 Results: energy – baseline heat balance

Before the implementation of the NextGen solutions (Kabisch 2016, Demoware):

→ In summer, the heat demand is below the produced heat amount

→ In winter, the heat demand is higher than the produced heat amount

7.1. Results and key performance indicators (KPIs)

Up to 25% increase in methane production rate during TPH operation

7.1. Results and key performance indicators (KPIs)

Organic loading rate ranges mainly between 1 and 3 kg DM/(m³*d)

→ Increase in methane production rate due to TPH

7.2. Results and key performance indicators (KPIs)

Full-scale nutrient recovery
GOAL: Phosphorus recovery

→ Recovery rate is still too low: crystal size is too small

7.3. Results and key performance indicators (KPIs)

Full-scale nutrient recovery

GOAL: Nitrogen recovery

■ Influent
■ Effluent
+ Recovery rate

→ Recovery rate is higher than required

→ Optimization in order to save energy and chemicals

8. Progress: energy & material

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 1 Braunschweig (DE) Location: WWTP Braunschweig	Sub-Task 1.3.2 Internal heat usage and heat management for two-stage digestion system & TPH	Three one-stage digesters; heat reuse from CHPs for tempering the digesters and the surrounding buildings	Two-stage digestion system with thermal pressure hydrolysis (TPH) between the two stages: higher heat demand due to TPH, reuse of excess heat from TPH and more available heat from CHP due to increased methane yield	Digestion system with TPH: TRL 8 → 9	On average: up to 250 m ³ /h methane production without TPH; with TPH increase to 330 m ³ /h	Biogas production: Up to 25% increase in methane production due to TPH.	Due to unexpected and necessary retrofitting measures for the plant and due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant was stopped for 3 months. Since October 2020, the recovery plant is in operation again.
	Sub-Task 1.4.7 Full-scale nutrient recovery from wastewater	Irrigation and fertilization of agricultural fields with WWTP effluent and digestate	Phosphorus recovery for struvite production	TRL 9	Around 250 t struvite (dry)/year equals to 30 t P/year and 15 t N/year	Struvite precipitation (≥90% of P recovered from P load to recovery unit)	
			Ammonia stripping for ammonium sulfate production	TRL 9	Around 2200 t ammonium sulfate solution (wet)/year equals to 170 t N/year	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (>85% of N recovered from N load to recovery unit)	

8. Progress – energy

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#1	<p>Braunschweig, Germany</p> <p>Location: WWTP Braunschweig</p> <p>Lead Partner: AVB</p> <p>Partners involved: KWB</p>	Sub-Task 1.3.2	Two-stage digestion system with thermal pressure hydrolysis (TPH) between the two stages: higher heat demand due to TPH, reuse of excess heat from TPH and more available heat from CHP due to increased methane yield	Due to unexpected and necessary retrofitting measures for the plant and due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant (incl. TPH) was stopped for 3 months. In July 2020, the recovery plant started operation again. However operation was paused several times afterwards as at TPH and screw extruder occurred leakages, clogging and error messages which needed to be solved by the manufacturing companies. Since October 2020 the plant is in full and continuous operation.	This task will still last 18 months as foreseen. However, the time period is shifted one year and will now finish in M36 instead of M24.

8. Progress - material

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#1	<p>Braunschweig, Germany</p> <p>Location: WWTP Braunschweig</p> <p>Lead Partner: AVB</p> <p>Partners involved: KWB</p>	Sub-Task 1.4.7	<p>Phosphorus recovery for struvite production</p> <p>Ammonia stripping for ammonium sulfate production</p>	<p>Due to unexpected and necessary retrofitting measures for the plant and due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant was stopped for 3 months. In July 2020, the recovery plant started operation again. However operation was paused several times afterwards as at TPH and screw extruder occurred leakages, clogging and error messages which needed to be solved by the manufacturing companies. Since October 2020 the plant is in full and continuous operation.</p>	<p>This task will still last 24 months as foreseen. However, the time period is postponed about 6 months and will now finish in M42 instead of M36.</p>

8. Next steps

Next steps planned: from November 2020 on

Task	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Commissioning struvite recovery unit												
Analysis internal heat management thermal hydrolysis + two stage digestion												
Different operational strategies internal heat management												
Analysis recovered products												
Optimization specifications recovered products												

8. Next steps

Planned timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Full-scale system for thermal hydrolysis, two-stage digestion and nutrient recovery via NH ₃ stripping and struvite precipitation will be commissioned successively, starting end of 2018	1.3.2	█							
Internal heat management will be analysed in the first two years of operation to cover the heat demand of thermal hydrolysis and two-stage digestion without using external fuels	1.3.2		█						
Different operational strategies will be checked to make maximum use of available heat (e.g. seasonal operation of heat storage, changing to thermophilic digestion, heat sale)	1.3.2			█					
Products of nutrient recovery (e.g. ammonium sulfate, struvite) will be analysed on a regular basis to provide data for risk assessment (WP2) and for checking legal conformity of products with existing rules	1.4.7			█					
Specifications of recovered fertilizers will be optimised (e.g. concentration, particle size, nutrient content) to match farmers demand, and potential options for product refinement will be checked	1.4.7			█					

Updated timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Full-scale system for thermal hydrolysis, two-stage digestion and nutrient recovery via NH ₃ stripping and struvite precipitation will be commissioned successively, starting end of 2019	1.3.2	█							
Internal heat management will be analysed in the first two years of operation to cover the heat demand of thermal hydrolysis and two-stage digestion without using external fuels	1.3.2				█				
Different operational strategies will be checked to make maximum use of available heat (e.g. seasonal operation of heat storage, changing to thermophilic digestion, heat sale)	1.3.2				█				
Products of nutrient recovery (e.g. ammonium sulfate, struvite) will be analysed on a regular basis to provide data for risk assessment (WP2) and for checking legal conformity of products with existing rules	1.4.7				█				
Specifications of recovered fertilizers will be optimised (e.g. concentration, particle size, nutrient content) to match farmers demand, and potential options for product refinement will be checked	1.4.7				█				

8. Next steps

	Task	Reason for modifications	Progress + next steps
T1.3.2	Initiate the demonstration of internal heat usage and heat management for two-stage digestion and sludge hydrolyses at Braunschweig (Ongoing / slight delay of partial tasks (rescheduled))	Some delay on the commissioning of full scale plant, but the demonstration schedule has been restructured to ensure the global objectives of the site; during construction phase several delays occurred due to problems of the technical finishing craft which laid to further delays of following works. The initial planned start of commissioning at the end of 2018 had to be changed to mid 2019. Due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant (incl. TPH) was stopped for 3 months as the danish manufacturing company of the TPH was not able to do several repairings and maintenances. In July 2020, the recovery plant started operation again. However operation was paused several times afterwards as at TPH and screw extruder occurred leakages, clogging and error messages which needed to be solved by the manufacturing companies. Since October 2020 the plant is in full and continuous operation. Nevertheless the delay has no consequences regarding the demonstration of the internal heat usage and heat management.	Construction phase including delays of several trades was finished at mid 2019. Commissioning began at August/September 2019. Analysis of the operation of the thermal pressure hydrolysis and the two stage digestion started in the first half of 2020. Due to COVID-19 situation analysis was paused and restarted in October 2020.
T1.4.7	Initiate the demonstration of full-scale nutrient recovery from wastewater and reuse in agriculture at Braunschweig (Ongoing / slight delay of partial tasks (rescheduled))	Some delay on the commissioning of full scale plant, but the demonstration schedule has been restructured to ensure the global objectives of the site; during construction phase several delays occurred due to problems of the technical finishing craft which laid to further delays of following works. The initial planned start of commissioning at the end of 2018 had to be changed to mid 2019. Nevertheless the delay has no consequences regarding the demonstration of the full-scale nutrient recovery from wastewater; Furthermore several problems occurred during commissioning of the struvite recovery plant due to unexpected blockage issues. Therefore the technical configuration and geometry of struvite recovery unit was adapted at January/February 2020. Due to COVID-19 situation, the operation of the whole recovery plant (incl. TPH) was stopped for 3 months as the danish manufacturing company of the TPH was not able to do several repairings and maintenances. In July 2020, the recovery plant started operation again. However operation was paused several times afterwards as at TPH and screw extruder occurred leakages, clogging and error messages which needed to be solved by the manufacturing companies. Since October 2020 the plant is in full and continuous operation. Nevertheless the delay has no consequences regarding the demonstration of the full-scale nutrient recovery.	Construction phase including delays of several trades was finished at mid 2019. Commissioning began at September/October 2019. Adaption of configuration and geometry of the struvite recovery unit was finished in February 2020. Constant operation of the struvite recovery unit with sufficient particle size is expected at end 2020.

#2.

Costa Brava (ES)

Tossa de Mar WRP

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Relevant data

6.4 hm³ water reused / year

Relevant sectors

Factory

Agriculture

Water treatment

Drinking water

Lead partners

Agència Catalana de l'Aigua

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/costa-brava-region/>

Touristic region located on the Mediterranean, characterized by high seasonal demand, frequent water scarcity episodes, also causing saltwater intrusion.

It is one of the first areas in the uptake of water reuse in Europe with 14 full-scale tertiary treatments that provide 4 hm³/year (2016) for agricultural irrigation, environmental uses, non-potable urban uses and, recently, indirect potable reuse.

1. General description of the site

In the case of Costa Brava site, a pilot plant integrated by ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules fitted with RO regenerated membranes was installed in December 2019 at the WWTP of Tossa de Mar.

The pilot plant was allocated after the sand filter of the tertiary treatment of the WWTP. It will operate for 2 years (2020-2021). During this period, the operation conditions of this new system will be evaluated, as well as the quality of the water obtained to be used for the irrigation of private gardens.

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

- ✓ Regenerate end-of-life reverse osmosis (RO) membranes to obtain different molecular cut-offs to be used in the multipurpose fit-for-use reclamation system. 2 year pilot.
- ✓ Produce fit-for-use water quality for sensitive uses to extend the use of reclaimed water in the area: irrigation of private gardens and, theoretically, indirect potable reuse through aquifer recharge.
- ✓ Integrated urban/regional water cycle optimisation including all the relevant actors.

- ✓ By this way, the time-life of RO membranes will be increased, and the generated quantity of this waste diminished.

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Costa Brava

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 2 Costa Brava (ES) Location: Tossa de Mar	Sub-Task 1.2.2 Integration of recycled membranes in multiquality - multipurpose water reuse	WWTP with a tertiary treatment integrated by a pre-chlorination treatment, a coagulation / flocculation process, a sand filter and UV lamp treatment. Pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project consists of an ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules that can treat up to 2 m ³ /h of water.	Refurbishment and adaptation of the pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project: ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules are fitted with reverse osmosis (RO) regenerated membranes used as a final treatment of urban effluents in the WWTP of Tossa de Mar to obtain a regenerated water for being used to irrigate private gardens.	TRL 5 → 7	Pilot plant which produces 2 m ³ /h of regenerated water	Regenerated water (2 m ³ /h) for private garden irrigation (RD 1620/2007, Spain)	Ongoing. Pilot plant refurbished, adapted and implemented.
	Sub-Task 1.2.2 Integration of recycled membranes in multiquality - multipurpose water reuse	Regenerated effluent from tertiary treatment is nowadays used for public garden irrigation.	Multi-purpose water reclamation and reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Irrigation of private gardens (which requires a higher quality of the effluent compared to the used for public garden irrigation, according to Spanish RD 1620/2007) - Theoretical study of indirect potable water reuse throughout the determination of the emergent pollutants in the regenerated effluent compared with current one. 	TRL 9		Theoretically: Indirect Potable Reuse by aquifers recharge	Start-up was foreseen on June 2020 (according to the initial timeline), but due to COVID-19, it will be delayed after June probably.

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new Nextgen solution

5. NextGen solutions

Principal and main characteristics of the pilot plant

The pilot plant (located within a sea container of 20 feet (6.05m)) is fed with water from the sand filter of the tertiary treatment of Tossa de Mar WWTP.

It consists of a 50 µm mesh filter to remove the coarse particulate matter coupled to a UF stage, where two modules are installed in parallel: one based on regenerated RO membranes and the other is a commercial one. Finally, it can be found the NF stage based on regenerated RO membranes.

The pilot plant has an estimated production flowrate of 2,2 m³/h. The water produced is disinfected by the online addition of sodium hypochlorite and it is stored in a 10m³ tank. This tank is placed in an easily accessible area, from where the water tank truck can pick it up and distribute it to the end-user sites. The regenerated water will be used for private garden irrigation.

5. NextGen solutions

P&I diagram of the pilot plant

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures of the pilot plant

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures of the pilot plant

5. NextGen solutions

6. Operational procedures

6.1. Pilot plant operation

During the pilot operation, the monitoring of the quality and quantity of regenerated water is foreseen. The parameters fixed by the Quality 1.1. of RD 1620/2007 as well as the screening of trace organic compounds (TrOCs) (pharmaceutical, EDCs, pesticides and the WL 2018 products) will be evaluated in the “NF permeate tank”.

In the end-user site, the free/total chlorine, turbidity, TSS, N and P are also foreseen to be quantified in order to ensure the water quality just before the irrigation of private gardens.

Table 1. Monitoring foreseen in the project framework.

Water type	Intestinal nematodes	Escherichia coli	Suspended solids	Turbidity	Legionella spp.	Free/Total chlorine	Other
Outlet of pilot plant (stored in the 10 m ³ tank)	Twice / month	Twice/ week	Once / week	Twice / week	Once / month	Twice / week	5 selected TrOC:s once/month Screening TrOCs: once / 3 month
End-user site	N/A	N/A	Occasionally (when water is discharged)	Occasionally (when water is discharged)	N/A	Twice / week	N, P (occasionally)

6. Operational procedures

6.2. Tools for environmental & economic impacts assessment at Costa Brava (WP2)

- Quantitative microbial risk assessment via the AquaNES online tool
- Life cycle assessment
- Life cycle costing
- Cost efficiency analysis
- Hydroptim system design of water supply
- This information will be collected in D2.2

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions

7.1 Specific KPIs

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#2 Costa Brava (ES)	Wastewater treatment and reuse	To increase the production of regenerated water for private garden irrigation	Water yield of the system [% of regenerated water produced for private garden irrigation]	0 %	> 70 %
		To reduce the salinity of the effluent	Salt rejection yield [% salt removal vs inlet flow]	0 %	> 80 %
		To reduce the content of trace organic compounds (TrOCs) of the regenerated water	Global removal yield for several priority/emergent pollutants [%]	0 % (To be updated with the current removal of WWTP)	> 90 %
		To reduce the TSS and turbidity of the effluent	TSS and turbidity removal yield vs inlet flow to the system [%]	0 % (To be updated with the current removal of WWTP)	> 95 %
		To reduce the pathogens content of the effluent	[<i>E.coli</i>] final effluent [CFU/100mL]	1	0
	[Intestinal nematodes] final effluent [egg/10L]		1	≤ 1	
	[<i>Legionella spp.</i>] final effluent [CFU/100mL]		< 100	< 100	
	Energy	To reduce electricity consumption of the Nextgen UF & NF processes compared with conventional ones	Electricity consumption [kWh/m ³ regenerated water]	2 kWh/m ³ (Garcia-Ivars 2017)	To be calculated once in stable operation
	Materials	Evaluation of the viability of the RO recycled membranes	Flux [l m ⁻² h ⁻¹] related to transmembrane pressure [bar]	13 lm ² h/bar (Garcia-Ivars 2017)	
			Salt rejection [%] compared to a commercial membrane of the same type	> 97% (NF270)	

7. Results

7.2. Characterization of inlet water to the pilot plant

Sampling campaigns

Start-up of the pilot plant

	Parameters and number of samples					
	Sampling 1	Sampling 2	Sampling 3	Sampling 4	Sampling 5	Sampling 6
	Des-18	March-19	Jul-19	Oct-19	Març-20	oct-20
Physicochemical parameters						
pH	0	1	1	1	1	1
CE	0	1	1	1	1	1
SDI (embrutiment membrana)	0	1	1	1	1	1
Turbidity	0	1	1	1	1	1
TSS	0	1	1	1	1	1
COD total	0	1	1	1	1	1
BOD ₅	0	1	1	1	1	1
DOC	0	1	1	1	1	1
TIC	0	1	1	1	1	1
Anions	0	1	1	1	1	1
Cations	0	1	1	1	1	1
Metals	0	1	1	1	1	1
Nitrogen total	0	1	1	1	1	1
P total	0	1	1	1	1	1
Free chlorine/Total chlorine	0	1	1	1	1	1
Microbiological parameters						
<i>E.coli</i>	0	0	1	1	1	1
<i>Legionella spp.</i>	0	0	1	1	1	1
Intestinal nematodes	0	0	1	1	1	1
CLOSTRIDIUM PERFRINGENS	0	0	1	1	1	1
BACTERIOFAGOS FECALES SOMATICOS	0	0	1	1	1	1
TrOCs						
Neonicotinoids - screening	5	1	1	1	No analized	1
Pesticides - screening	1	1	1	1		1
EDCs - screening	5	1	1	1		1
Pharmaceutical compounds - screening	5	1	1	1		1
Amoxicillin	5	1	1	1		1

7. Results

7.2. Characterization of inlet water to the pilot plant

PHARMACEUTICAL COMPOUNDS ● Guide values of theoretical toxicology (obtained from various literature sources) of sustained human intake over time supplied by Health Department of Catalunya. Conservative values (safety margin: 1log)

7. Results

7.2. Characterization of inlet water to the pilot plant

PESTICIDES COMPOUNDS

..... Limit of RD140/2003 related to drinking water

7. Results

7.2. Characterization of inlet water to the pilot plant

● Guide values of theoretical toxicology (obtained from various literature sources) of sustained human intake over time supplied by Health Department of Catalunya. Conservative values (safety margin: 1log)

EDCs

Other compounds

7. Results

7.3. Selection of TrOCs to be determined monthly

N° Code

- 1 [TrOC] effluent from sand filter > limit fixed by the legislation or [TrOC] effluent from sand filter > guide value proposed
- 2 [TrOC] regenerated water > limit fixed by the legislation or [TrOC] regenerated water > guide value proposed
- 3 Removal from NF with RO regenerated membranes < 90%
- 4 [TrOC] > 100 ng/L in all the sampling campaigns
- 5 TrOC included in the Watch List 2018

- 1. **Caffeine (EDC)**
- 2. **Benzotriazole-1H (EDC)**
- 3. **AMPA (Pesticide)**
- 4. **2,4-D (Pesticide)**
- 5. **Azithromycin (WL 2018) (Pharmaceutical compound)**

7. Results

7.4. Preliminary experiments with regenerated RO membranes

High removal efficiencies for the most part of TrOC

7. Results

7.5. Preliminary tests with the pilot plant

Operated at 70% conversion – 13 lmh

Fouling observed in the membrane

	Turbidity (NTU)		SDI	Conductivity (mS/cm)	
	Mean	St. Dev		Mean	St. Dev
Feed of SF	6,96	1,38			
Feed to UF	5,41	0,81	>5		
Permeate UF	0,50	0,37	1,7	1,297007	0,010531
Permeate regenerated NF	0,33	0,15		0,251437	0,001177

8. Progress and next steps planned

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	Status	Status/Contingency plan
# 2 Costa Brava (ES) Location: Tossa de Mar	Sub-Task 1.2.2 Integration of recycled membranes in multiquality-multipurpose water reuse	WWTP with a tertiary treatment integrated by a pre-chlorination treatment, a coagulation / flocculation process, a sand filter and UV lamp treatment. Pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project consists of an ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules that can treat up to 2 m ³ /h of water.	Refurbishment and adaptation of the pilot plant from ZEROBRINE Project: ultrafiltration (UF) and nanofiltration (NF) modules are fitted with reverse osmosis (RO) regenerated membranes used as a final treatment of urban effluents in the WWTP of Tossa de Mar to obtain a regenerated water for being used to irrigate private gardens.	The pilot plant is already installed in the Tossa de Mar WWTP from February 2020. The start-up of the pilot plant was planned for June 2020 (M24). However, due to SARS-CoV-2 restrictions, the start-up of the pilot plant experimented some delay. So at the end, the pilot plant is in operation during September 2020.	Ongoing. Pilot plant refurbished, adapted, implemented and in operation. It is foreseen to shorten the time dedicated to evaluate the several types of regenerated membranes: 21 months instead of 24 months. So there is still enough time to properly evaluate the proposed technologies.
	Sub-Task 1.2.2 Integration of recycled membranes in multiquality-multipurpose water reuse	Regenerated effluent from tertiary treatment is nowadays used for public garden irrigation.	Multi-purpose water reclamation and reuse: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Irrigation of private gardens (which requires a higher quality of the effluent compared to the used for public garden irrigation, according to Spanish RD 1620/2007) - Theoretical study of indirect potable water reuse throughout the determination of the emergent pollutants in the regenerated effluent compared with current one. 		

8. Progress and next steps planned

Planned timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Establishment of current status (baseline conditions) and design of the pilot reclamation scheme for irrigation of private gardens with local operator	1.2.2	Yellow							
Obtaining end-of-life membranes and optimization of regeneration conditions at bench scale to reach UF and NF conditions.	1.2.2		Green						
Regeneration and testing of 8-inch modules.	1.2.2				Green				
Refurbishment and adaptation of pilot plant from ZEROBRINE project	1.2.2				Green				
Installation and commissioning of pilot plant at Tossa de Mar WWTP	1.2.2				Green				
Operation of water reuse pilot. Evaluation of performance according to Spanish regulations for private irrigation and study of specific microbial (UF evaluation)	1.2.2					Green			
Operation of water reuse pilot. Evaluation of performance according to Spanish regulations for other uses (i.e. aquifer recharge) and study of specific microbial and trace pollutants removal (NF-RO evaluation)	1.2.2							Green	
Assessment of results and extrapolation to other WWTP in the demo site	1.2.2							Yellow	

Updated timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Establishment of current status (baseline conditions) and design of the pilot reclamation scheme for irrigation of private gardens with local operator	1.2.2	Yellow							
Obtaining end-of-life membranes and optimization of regeneration conditions at bench scale to reach UF and NF conditions.	1.2.2		Green						
Regeneration and testing of 8-inch modules.	1.2.2				Green				
Refurbishment and adaptation of pilot plant from ZEROBRINE project	1.2.2				Green				
Installation and commissioning of pilot plant at Tossa de Mar WWTP	1.2.2				Green				
Operation of water reuse pilot. Evaluation of performance according to Spanish regulations for private irrigation and study of specific microbial and trace organic compounds removals (NF fitted with RO regenerated membranes & UF with comercial membranes)	1.2.2					Green			
Operation of water reuse pilot. Evaluation of performance according to Spanish regulations for private irrigation and study of specific microbial and trace organic compounds removals (UF & NF fitted with RO regenerated membranes)	1.2.2							Green	
Operation of water reuse pilot. Evaluation of performance according to Spanish regulations for other uses (i.e. aquifer recharge) and study of specific microbial and trace pollutants removals (best RO regenerated membranes used to fit the UF & NF modules)	1.2.2								Green
Assessment of results and extrapolation to other WWTP in the demo site	1.2.2							Yellow	

Westland Region

Circular solutions for

Water

Energy

Relevant data

0,5 M households served

100-150 PJ Excess heat supply (industry near outside Westland)

600 horticulture companies, 2300 ha

120-75 PJ Excess heat demand (horticulture, cities)

Lead partners

Horticulture

Heavy port industry

Chemicals industry

Drinking water companies

Introduction to the demo case: <https://nextgenwater.eu/westland-region/>

1. General description of the site

Delfland is a dense region of urban and industrial areas and greenhouse complexes (Westland).

The overall water management system is a **linear** system: water enters the region, is used and discharged outside of the region. The surface water system is based on water level management.

Water balance (average)
Delfland region

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

2.1. Current situation greenhouse horticulture industry Westland

Horticulture uses rainwater (collected in shallow basins) for irrigation but in times of shortages this is supplemented with brackish groundwater (desalinated by RO).

Inside the greenhouses, water is recirculated, evaporated water is condensed and emission of nutrients and pesticides minimised. Final wastewater treatment to reduce PPP/pesticides emissions.

Natural gas and electricity are used for heating and lighting. CO₂ of the CHP is used to increase crop yields.

Block diagram of the pre-existing treatment scheme in horticulture

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

2.2. Current situation urban area Delfland region

In the urban areas (Rotterdam, The Hague, Delft), water level management is in place with the purpose of flood prevention.

High quality drinking water is provided from treated surface water (Dunea, Evides) and recovered materials are brokered to end users (AquaMinerals).

At the 4 WWTPs, advanced treatment systems are in place, including biogas production and nutrient recovery. Effluent is discharged to the sea (HH Delfland)

WWTP Harnaschpolder

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

2.3. Current situation for ASR and ATEs

ASR		Parameter	Mean value for 2018
Water yield of the system	Current system	Rainfall climatology of the area (mm/year or L/m ² /year)	720
		Volume of water recovered vs rainfall (m ³ /year)	6,500,000
Water quality	Quality of rainwater harvested	COD (mg O ₂ /l)	32
		BOD ₅ (mg O ₂ /l)	5.7
		pH	6.2
		TSS (mg/l)	17
		N Kjeldahl (mg N/l)	1.9
		Total nitrogen (mg N/l)	1.9
Energy consumption	Current water storage / infiltration / pumping system	Total phosphorus (mg P/l)	0.4
		Whole system (kWh/m ³)	0.55

ATES		Parameter	Mean value for 2018
Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage systems (ATES)	Primary energy	Reduction of consumption (%)	50
	Thermal	T cold well (°C)	5
		T warm well (°C)	18
		Heat demand warm well (TJ)	23
		Cooling demand cold well (TJ)	16

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

The main objective of the Westland demo case is the **demonstration of an integrated approach for a circular water system at the Delfland region.**

In the region already numerous initiatives exist of circular technologies related to e.g. rainwater harvesting and reuse in horticulture, aquifer thermal energy storage, urban water management and resource recovery from WWTPs.

In NextGen, a regional management strategy for a circular water-energy-materials system will be implemented at regional scale, supported by a CoP to have active cooperation between stakeholders.

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

The key innovations and actions:

1. For the transition towards a more **circular water system** in the Delfland region, an integrated assessment of performance of technologies and strategies will be done.

This assessment will include (T1.2.1):

- the use of alternative water sources (through region-wide rainwater storage and reuse using large scale *Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR)* systems and *reuse of WWTP effluent*) and advanced water treatment systems (*recycling and purification*) for the **horticulture** sector,
- and several **urban** water management systems (*rainwater harvesting, grey water recycling, green roofs and domestic water saving*).

2. For an integrated **water-energy** approach in the Delfland region, the contribution of *Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage* systems (ATES) to the overall energy balance will be assessed.

This assessment will include (T1.3.5):

- a feasibility study of a *High Temperature-Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage* system (HT-ATES) at the **horticulture** Koppert Cress, and the role HT-ATES could play in the South-Holland heat roundabout.

3. For the upscaling of the **recovery of materials and resources** from the water system, a novel business model of reused materials brokerage will be demonstrated (T5.1)

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Westland

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
<p>#3 Westland, Netherlands</p> <p>Location: Delfland region. It is the catchment area of the Waterboard Delfland</p>	Sub-Task 1.2.1	<p>One ASR showcase in the Delfland region. Total area 27 ha.</p> <p>Location: Groeneweg 75, 'S Gravenzande</p>	Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems	TRL 7/8 → 9	Average of 8500 m ³ /ha/year	<p>Volume of rainwater collected from the roofs and partly stored in aboveground basins and recovered for horticulture irrigation.</p> <p>Region-wide water balance (from linear to circular; m³/y).</p>	<p>Ongoing.</p> <p>In NextGen a more circular water concept for the Delfland region (initiate, propagate, analyze) is demonstrated. In the region several initiatives are already in development, such as Coastar (upscaling ASR) and Waterbank (solution for discharge of brine in the subsurface).</p> <p>The options to use alternative water sources for the horticulture sector (region-wide rainwater use through ASR and reuse of WWTP-effluent) and urban water management systems (rainwater harvesting, grey water recycling, domestic water saving, green roofs) are being assessed and discussed with stakeholders.</p>

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
<p>#3 Westland, Netherlands</p> <p>Location: Delfland region. It is the catchment area of the Waterboard Delfland</p>	Sub-Task 1.2.1	No wastewater purification systems at the horticulture companies before 2018	Water recycling and individual/collective water purification system for horticulture	TRL 9 TRL 6 → 8	<p>Average use of water 7500 m³/ha/year in company</p> <p>Waste water stream horticulture varies from 0 – 500 m³/ha/year.</p>	<p>Water use (m³/ha/y) and water efficiency (condensate and use evaporate water). Wastewater treated (m³/ha/y).</p>	<p>Ongoing.</p> <p>Almost all greenhouses in the region (total 2500 ha) already have cyclic irrigation water streams.</p> <p>There is a new obligation by law to have a water purification system or zero emission (realization period (2018 – 2021). Currently the horticulture farmers are opting for either individual, collective, or central collective wastewater treatment.</p> <p>Within NextGen, the options for enhanced water treatment systems (recycling and purification) in horticulture are included in the assessment of a closed water system in Delfland (see above).</p>

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
#3 Westland, Netherlands Location: Delfland region. It is the catchment area of the Waterboard Delfland	Sub-Task 1.3.5	Several in operation	Heat harvesting unit (ATES)	TRL 5 → 7	ATES systems (TJ)	Region-wide water-energy balance. Common practice in rural/urban area.	Ongoing. In Delfland region several ATES systems are in operation. Within NextGen, the contribution of ATES systems to the region-wide water-energy balance (including the heat roundabout) is being assessed. In particular, the option to enhance ATES into HT-ATES systems is demonstrated (see below).
	Sub-Task 1.3.5	Pilot set-up	High Temperature-Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage system (HT-ATES)	TRL 4 → 6	Pilot location: heat demand 23 TJ, cold demand 16 TJ	Energy efficiency (energy and exergy produced/stored, %).	Ongoing. The HT-ATES at horticulture Koppert Cress is in operation and within NextGen the performance is being monitored. The knowledge gained from this test location will be used to assess the region-wide water-energy balance. Next step to make it possible by law and license.

5. NextGen solutions

For the transition towards a more **circular water system** in the Delfland region (T1.2.1):

- Assessment of the contribution of several technology options to further close the water system, by UWOT modelling of scenarios.

Scenarios include:

- extension of large scale rainwater harvesting through *Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR)*
- water recycling and individual/collective water purification system at horticulture industry
- the reuse of WWTP effluent for horticulture
- *urban* water management systems (rainwater harvesting, grey water recycling, green roofs and domestic water saving).

For an integrated **water-energy** approach in the Delfland region (T1.3.5):

- Assessment of the contribution of *Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage* systems (ATES) to the overall energy balance
- Feasibility study of a *High Temperature-Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage* system (HT-ATES) at the *horticulture* Koppert Cress

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Towards a circular regional water system

Baseline scenarios

- Baseline conditions for Westland reflect the present-day state of the regional water system, including both urban and rural (horticulture) uses.
- Reflects current water system technologies already in place: central networks for DW/WW, shallow RW basins for horticulture.
- Data from multiple (open) sources are collected to form baseline conditions. A relevant geodatabase about Westland is populated that will be also used for modeling tasks (WP2).

Baseline condition	Sources
Household consumption details (uses and frequencies of use)	National statistics (WaterStatistieken)
Number of households, household types	cbs.nl (Provincie Zuid-Holland) hhdelfland.nl (Delfland Water Board)
Rainfall (daily time-series), last 30 years	KNMI
Spatial characteristics of urban areas (pervious/impervious) Land uses in urban and horti areas	hddelfland.nl (Delfland Water Board) pdok.nl (Dutch open datasets) zuid-holland.nl (Provincie Zuid-Holland) CORINE land cover (EU dataset)
Spatial characteristics of rural areas Number of greenhouses Greenhouse demands (daily time-series)	Past KWR consultancy (COASTAR, Waterbanking) Internal KWR data

Baseline
Households follow linear WM
Greenhouses rely on shallow RW basins

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Towards a circular regional water system

Baseline scenarios

The baseline conditions geodatabase for Westland feeds into the Westland UWOT model of WP2.

Baseline

hh's follow linear WM
Greenhouses rely on shallow RW basins

geodatabase

data in

data out

UWOT topology

all	Individual GH Scale				GH system scale		
	Total demands - all (L/day)	Unit demands [m3/day]	Water storage, GH - Shallow Basin (L)	GH Shallow Basin Spills (L/day)	Unit GH Deficits Asked from system (L/day)	GH dmd to WaterUtility Log (L/day)	GH (Rural) Runoff to Outlet (L/day)
18.00	147862546.00	18.51736305	0.00	0.00	8517.36	10995916.00	0.00
18.00	147862546.00	18.51736305	Note: Columns W:AA are ONLY for the scenario of 0% ASR, 100%				0.00
						1824321.00	0.00
						0.00	0.00

spreadsheet

- Pairing with a spreadsheet database for model I/O.

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Towards a circular regional water system

Baseline scenarios

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Towards a circular regional water system

Circular scenarios

A first draft of six scenarios that represent different circular futures:

- different mixture of techs in urban settings (RWH/GWR)
- different mixture of techs in horticulture (RWH/use of ASR technology)
- one scenario with collective water purification system for horticulture that connects urban settings and horticulture (WWTP reuse to GH)

These scenarios represent different policy pathways that materialize to technological decisions – improvements on either urban or horticulture water systems, or both.

Scenarios are discussed against key stakeholders in collaboration with WP3 (Westland CoP, Sept. 2020) – certain alterations will be made based on stakeholder feedback.

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Water recycling and collective water purification system for horticulture.

- ✓ Target: Zero emission of nutrients and pesticides in 2027;
- ✓ Water purification obligation from 1-1-21
- ✓ Participation of 1100 ha horticulture area
- ✓ In 2020 a decision was taken to built an additional treatment step (O3) at WWTP Nieuwe Waterweg (Hoek van Holland) as collective wastewater treatment facility for Westland horticulture (by 2022).
- ✓ Wastewater will be purified at Nieuwe Waterweg and Groote Lucht to irrigation water quality for the horticulture (reverse osmosis)

WWTP Hoek van Holland

5. NextGen solutions

5.2/5.3. Water and energy storage systems for horticulture.

Extension of ASR (water T1.2.1) and ATEs (energy T1.3.5) systems at greenhouse horticulture industry

Assessment of the contribution of Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) and Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage systems (ATES) to the regional water and energy balance.

Scheme of the new NextGen solution

5. NextGen solutions

5.2. Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems.

Principle ASR in the horticulture

- ✓ Water quality demand for irrigation: $[Na] < 0.5 \text{ mM}$ → Rainwater: primary irrigation water source for the horticulture
- ✓ By the ASR the excess of rainwater (winter) is temporarily stored in an aquifer (depth app. -20m to -40 m below surface) so that it can be recovered in summer period as irrigation water.
- ✓ The rainwater is collected from the roofs (area about 2500 ha) and partly stored in aboveground basins (average 800 m³/ha).
- ✓ Through ASR, almost all the annual rainfall (average about 8500 m³/ha) can be harvested. Moreover, the infiltration of freshwater limits also further salinization of the aquifer.
- ✓ One ASR showcase in the Delfland region. Total area 27 ha

Only extraction from Aq. 1 and concentrate injection in Aq. 2.

ASR in Aq. 1 and concentrate injection in Aq. 2

1. Roof. Rain water harvesting
2. Basin. Water collection
3. Sand filtration
4. ASR. Subsurface water storage and recovery

5. NextGen solutions

5.2. Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems.

Water banking to counteract salinization and flooding

Storing collected rainwater in the subsurface may help to counteract groundwater salinization and provide space in the basins in which peak rainfall can be collected

However, recovery of stored water from brackish aquifers is difficult, so an incentive is lacking. Such an incentive can be created through water banking: groundwater extraction becomes conditional to rainwater infiltration.

This concept is further investigated for several scenarios

- Water balances, including system efficiency and overflow during rainfall events
- Effects on groundwater salinity
- Costs and (social) benefits
- Governance and legal possibilities
- Roadmap to implementation

5. NextGen solutions

5.2. Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems.

Video of Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) water banking system in development in Westland

5. NextGen solutions

5.3. High temperature Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (HT-ATES)

ATES Heat harvesting unit

In Westland, several Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage systems are in operation.

In ATES, regular plate heat exchangers are used to harvest heat.

Within NextGen:

1) The contribution of ATES to the regional energy balance is assessed.

A heat demand and supply map is prepared.

2) The feasibility of converting ATES into High Temperature ATES is studied.

At the horticulture Koppert-Cress a HT-ATES is piloted and its performance monitored.

5. NextGen solutions

5.3. High temperature Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (HT-ATES)

HT-ATES installed at horticulture

5. NextGen solutions

5.3. High temperature Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage

HT-ATES installed at horticulture

HT-ATES at Koppert Cress

Several heat exchangers in plant room

6. Operational procedures

6.1 Monitoring HT-ATES performance

Flow measurement in ATES well

6. Operational procedures

6.2. Tools for environmental & economic impacts assessment at Westland (WP2)

Water cycle tools:

- UWOT – KWR and Hydroptim - ADASA
- UWOT modelling will be used to model the current linear water system in the Delfland region and to simulate different scenarios towards a more circular system. This model will provide information on the effects on water quantity, including relevant consequences related to climate change (runoff) and financial dimensions.
- The Hydroptim modelling will add to this the energy implications of the circular water scenarios

Risk assessment:

- QMRA, supported with measurements – KWB & KWR
- Water quality related effects of the scenarios will be included, specifically by performing a microbiological risk assessment of effluent reuse for horticulture.
- This information will be collected in D2.2

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions (actual vs expected)

7.1 Specific KPIs

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
3 Westland Region (NL)	Wastewater treatment	To reduce the emission of PPPs/pesticides in surface water	Water purification units installed on various scale levels (individual/ collective/ central collective)	Removal pesticides <50%	Removal pesticides>> 95% (law rule)
	Rainwater harvesting	To increase the self sufficiency of fresh water in Delfland (Westland) region	% rainwater used for water related functions in cities, horticulture, etc.	Horticulture: 30-70% used but increasing salinity of aquifer. Cities: <1%	Horticulture: 30-70% but no increase in salinity of aquifer. Cities: scenario for 25% households with RWH.
	Energy	To develop a High Temperature ATES system	Efficiency comparison with ATES	T < 20C Cooling demand 6TJ Heating demand 8TJ Heat recovery factor: 0,6-0,7	T : 45-80C Cooling demand 16TJ Heating demand 23TJ Heat recovery factor: 0,8-0,9

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions

7.2. Circular water system – preliminary scenario result

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions

7.3. Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems: Water Banking

Assessment results

It is possible to 'compensate' all net extraction with infiltration if about half of the horticultural companies will infiltrate excess rain water.

If companies work together or if other roofs (large industry) are used as well, the number of infiltration locations can be greatly reduced, up to about 150 locations.

Overflow to surface water is strongly reduced, even for large precipitation events.

Extra 'tweaking' (such as including weather forecast) can result in more efficiency

Water balance of Westland horticultural companies	Reference scenario (current situation)	Waterbank basic scenario
Surface horticultural companies (ha)	2431	
Precipitation on roof (Mm ³ /j)	21.6	
Retention on roof (Mm ³ /j)	2.7	
Net precipitation in basin (Mm ³ /j)	18.9	
Irrigation demand (Mm ³ /j)	17.7	
Irrigation water from groundwater (RO) (Mm ³ /j)	3.7	5.0
Number of horticultural companies	1291	
No. companies that infiltrate surplus rainwater	0	600
Infiltration (Mm ³ /j)	0.0	5.0
Evaporation from basins (Mm ³ /j)	0.2	
Overflow	1.7	1.7

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions

7.4. High temperature Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (HT-ATES)

Energy balance

The heat demand and supply in the Delfland region has been mapped.

Next step is to assess the contribution of (HT-) ATES to the regional energy balance.

7. Results and Specific KPIs of the NextGen solutions

7.4. High temperature Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (HT-ATES)

Warm wells are installed in 2 different aquifers, DTS monitoring is installed at 4 locations from the well. Results below, to be extended and further analyze later.

At 5m distance a monitoring well is placed for taking groundwater samples

Temperature profiles: Oct-19 - sept-20

Cross section monitoring

8. Progress and next steps planned

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#3	Westland Region (NL)	Sub-Task 1.2.1	Aquifer Storage & Recovery (ASR) systems	No deviations	None
		Sub-Task 1.2.1	Water recycling and collective water purification system for horticulture	No deviations	None
		Sub-Task 1.3.5	Heat harvesting unit	No deviations	None
		Sub-Task 1.3.5	High Temperature-Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage system (HT-ATES)	No deviations	None

8. Progress and next steps planned

- M30 - • T1.2.1 modelling circular scenarios & assessment of ASR contribution to regional water balance
- M36: • T1.3.5 monitoring results of HT-ATES pilot plant at Koppert Cress & assessment of (HT)ATES contribution to regional energy balance

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M30	M31-M36	M37-M48
Set up of assessment tool for monitoring water cycle performance by appointing Key Performance Indicators (KPI) eg. percentage rainwater harvested, water quality, resource recovery products	1.2.1					
Assessment of water management conditions of the Westland case (performance) and input to Technology Evidence Base.	1.2.1					
Conclusive first results for Westland case: lessons learned and proposed integrated management of alternative water sources.	1.2.1					
Comparative analysis with Gotland case for providing guidance on how to replicate the models in other regions.	1.2.1					
Assessment of the Westland integrated watermanagement approach as best practice for closing the water cycle	1.2.1					
Monitoring performance High Temperature- Aquifer Thermal Energy Storage (HT-ATES) at horticulture location Koppert Cress Westland. Providing results to the Technology Evidence Base.	1.3.5					
Preparing the energy balance of and the contribution of HT-ATES for the heat roundabout. Conclusive first results.	1.3.5					
Assessment of HT-ATES pilot results and feasibility extrapolation to the heat roundabout in province South-Holland. Developing best practice of closing water related energy cycle.	1.3.5					

#4. Altenrhein Switzerland

Circular solutions for

Materials

Relevant data

WWTP: 100,000 PE; 300,000 PE (sludge treatment)

Relevant sectors

Water treatment

Horticulture

Energy

Lead partner:

Other partners:

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/altenrhein/>

1. General description of the site

WWTP: 100,000 PE; 300,000 PE (sludge treatment)

Primary treatment:

bar screens, sand trap, primary clarifier

Secondary treatment:

nitrification, denitrification, enhanced biological phosphorus removal, secondary clarifier

Sludge treatment:

anaerobic digestion & sludge drying

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

1. Production of granular activated carbon (GAC) via pyrolysis of dried sludge with local biomass with a subsequent activation and granulation
2. Production of PK-fertilizer via pyrolysis of sewage sludge with a additional potassium source
3. Ammonia recovery via a hollow fiber membrane contactor for ammonium sulfate production

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Altenrheini

4. Summary Table: material

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 4 Altenrhein (CH) Location: WWTP in Altenrhein	Sub-Task 1.4.1 Large scale demonstration of ammonium recovery by HFMC	Liquor from sludge dewatering returns to the WWTP	Implementation of a hollow fiber membrane contactor for ammonia recovery as $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	TRL 7 → 8	14 m ³ /h	Production of ammonium sulfate (fertilizer)	Ongoing. The construction of the stripping plant was delayed due to interactions with the construction of a micropollutant elimination plant in Altenrhein.
	Sub-Task 1.4.2 P-recovery by thermochemical treatment of sewage sludge	Incineration of the dried sludge at the cement factory	P recovery via pyrolysis as PK-fertilizer or NPK(S)-fertilizer	TRL 5 → 7	Input: 20-50 kg/h	Phosphorus in sludge modified and purified for reuse as market grade PK-fertilizer	Ongoing. PK- fertilizer preparatory trials lasted longer than expected.
	Sub-Task 1.4.3 Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC)	Filtration with commercial GAC after ozonation	Production of renewable GAC via pyrolysis, activation & granulation	TRL 5 → 6	Input: 1 kg/h	Renewable GAC used for micropollutants removal	Ongoing. Corona-related delays in pilot trials due to limited availability of production and testing facilities. Long-term tests planned 18 months starting M25, might have to be shortened. However evaluation of long term tests after 12 or 15 months also possible.

5. NextGen solutions

6. Large scale demonstration of ammonium recovery Production plant and operational procedure

Construction largely finalized - planned commissioning: **Feb 2021 (M32)**

Program

- Optimize process parameters (temperature, pH, centrate flow)
- Determine KPI (area specific ammonia mass transfer, absolute ammonia yield, yield specific caustic soda and heat consumption)
- Granulation tests, NPK(S) fertilizer

Collaboration FHNW and AVA with expertise from EAWAG and Alpha Wassertechnik

6. Large scale demonstration of ammonium recovery P&I diagram and design parameters of the plant

Elimination Parameters	Unit	Value
Nitrogen recovery yield	%	75
Minimum concentration nitrogen in fertilizer	%	3.5
Availability of production plant	%	85

Dimension Parameters	Unit	Value
Flow	m ³ /h	14
CSB concentration	mg/l	1'700
N-NH ₄ concentration	mg/l	900 ± 200
GUS concentration	mg/l	800
Temperature	°C	14
pH	-	8

6. Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC) Pictures and operational procedure

All methods have been tested with two renewable materials (FHNW):

- Pyrolysis
- Activation
- Performance
- Physical and chemical characterization

1st phase - Parameter screening

- DSC/TGA plus adsorption (UV 254)
- Upscaling to pilot (1 kg/h) to verify surface area, porosity, hardness, density

2nd phase - Production of optimised GAC

- 2x 150 L
- Sewage sludge, CO₂, 800°C
- Cherry pits, H₂O, 1000°C
- Reference Chemviron Cyclocarb

GAC from sewage sludge
after pyrolysis

6. Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC) Flow scheme of the pyrolysis

Multiple production parameters are considered:

1. Feedstock material (dried sewage sludge and cherry pits)
2. Conditions of pyrolysis and activation (temperature, residence time, activating gas)

Quality of GAC is assessed based on:

1. Adsorption capacity
2. Physical properties (hardness, surface, porosity, density)

6. Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC) Production of SS and CP GACs

Dried SS from AVA
Altenrhein

**PYREKA
Agroscope
Pyrolysis**

GAC after pyrolysis

Sieving

SS_GAK (~ 65 kg)

Cherry pits

**Milling and
sieving**

Milled and sieved
cherry pits

DBI Virtuhcon

Pyrolysis

CP_GAC after pyrolysis

**Sieving and
conditioning**

6. Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC) Pilot experiments operational procedure

Long term tests

Goals

- 1. To assess the performance of renewable GAC at pilot scale over 12 months of operation
- 2. To investigate on biofilm development over time (BAC)

Methodology

Operate the system (O_3 + GAC) at 80% OMPs removal. Three consecutive phases are defined

1st ph. : Standard (EBCT 20', 2 mg O_3 /L)

2nd ph. : Adjust EBCT to achieve 80% elimination

3rd ph. : Adjust O_3 dosage to achieve 80% elimination

6. Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC) Pilot experiments operational procedure

The OMPs elimination of the GAC filters is monitored over time at different operating modes (i.e. EBCT, and O_3 dosage)

Monitoring of the pilots

- Performance of the O_3 +GAC system (i.e. Organic micropollutant (OMPs) elimination by LC MS, and UV adsorption)
- Operating period of renewable GAC (i.e. carbon loss in the effluent)
- Biofilm formation (5-7 samples/yr) (TGA, flow cytometry, SEM, NGS)

6. PK fertilizer Picture of pilot plant

Feeder
Gasifier
Filter
Steam unit
Afterburner

Pyrolysis unit

6. PK fertilizer Preliminary pilot experiments

Experiment with start up phase , gasification phase and cool down phase with biomass

6. PK fertilizer Operational procedure for nextGen

Burn Out

- **Improve further by adaptation of fluidization medium at bottom**
- **Goal: < 0.2% TOC**
- **PAK: not detectable**

P-Availability

- **Residence time to be increased to allow K for Ca replacement reaction**

Operating Conditions

- **Bed material replacement to be improved by more efficient screening, smaller bed**

Reconstruction of Pilot Plant

- **Decrease of diameter in certain areas**
- **Additional section for burn out improvement**
- **Improved screening system for bed material/ash**

6. Operational procedures and methodologies

The parameters of material recovery procedures are monitored according to the specific requirements in order to ensure the quality standards of the products.

	Flow rates	N concentrations
(NH₄)₂SO₄	Wastewater influent to WWTP	
	Sludge input of third parties	
	Liquor to ammonia stripping unit	
	Effluent from ammonia stripping unit	
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄ (material product)	
	Flow rates	P concentrations
PK fertilizer	Wastewater influent to WWTP	
	Sewage sludge to mixing unit	
	PK fertilizer (material product)	

6. Operational procedures and methodologies

The parameters of material recovery procedures are monitored according to the specific requirements in order to ensure the quality standards of the products.

GAC	Adsorption capacity compared to that of commercially available GAC [%] via active surface (BJH)
	Lifetime until renewal compared to commercially available GAC indicated as BV (for removal > 80%, EBCT)

→ The testing of the GAC includes the use of the GAC filtration after ozonation. This will be evaluated for both conventional and renewable GAC.

	Removal rates
Micropollutants	12 micropollutants in the Swiss regulation. https://www.news.admin.ch/newsd/message/attachments/41551.pdf

→ Removal rates of the system will be compared to the results of the system in Costa Brava CS#2 for Diclofenac, Benzotriazole, Carbamazepine

6. Operational procedures and methodologies: Tools (WP2)

In the frame of WP2, different tools will be applied at the case study in Altenrhein:

- Quantitative chemical risk assessment for PK fertilizer
- Life cycle assessment
- Life cycle costing
- Cost efficiency analysis

The results are elaborated in WP2 and will be presented in D2.1 and D2.2.

7. Results: Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC)

TGA Analysis of pilot materials activated @ 900°C 10':

- Sewage sludge GAC (SS) with 10-15% «anorganic carbon» content
- Cherry pit GAC (CP) with 90% «anorganic carbon» content

7. Results: Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC)

Sewage sludge GAC with higher density than reference
Cherry pit GAC with lower density than reference

7. Results: PK fertilizer

Continuous operation was demonstrated

- **within an operating range of 340 to 110% of design throughput**
- **startup/shutdown demonstrated**
- **Good Burnout**

Heavy metals limits according to European Fertilizer product regulation achieved to a large extent

Phosphate plant availability too low compared with expectation

7. Results: specific KPIs (actual vs expected)

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#4 Alten- rhein (CH)	Materials	Recovery of ammonia via HFMC	Nitrogen recovery rate [%] related to the inflow liquor to the recovery system	0	75
		PK fertilizer production	Phosphorus recovery rate [%] related to the influent of the WWTP and the sludge input of third parties	0	100
			Plant availability of the P (P_{NAC}) [%]	n.a. (cement)	80
		Renewable GAC production	Active surface (BJH) [m^2/g]	1000	200-1000
	EBCT [min]		20	20	
	Lifetime until renewal [number of bed volumes (BV)] for micropollutant removal > 80%		80'000	25'000	

8. Progress and next steps

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#4	Altenrhein, Switzerland	Sub-Task 1.4.1 Large scale demonstration of ammonium recovery by HFMC	Liquor from sludge dewatering returns to the WWTP	The construction of the stripping plant was delayed because of interactions with the construction of a micropollutant elimination plant in Altenrhein.	However, this still leaves enough time for the production of ammonium sulfate as fertilizer, and the piloting of the P recovery.
	Location: Altenrhein WWTP	Sub-Task 1.4.2 P-recovery by thermochemical treatment of sewage sludge	Incineration of the dried sludge at the cement factory	PK- fertilizer preparatory trials were longer than expected	
	Lead Partner: FHNW Partners involved: AVA, CTU	Sub-Task 1.4.3 Renewable granular activated carbon (GAC)	Filtration with commercial GAC after ozonation	Corona-related delays in pilot trials due to limited availability of production and testing facilities. Long-term tests planned 18 months starting M25, might have to be shortened. However, evaluation of long term tests after 12 or 15 months also possible.	Subcontracting of GAC production

8. Progress and next steps

Planned timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Preparation/adaption of ammonia stripping plant	1.4.1		█	█					
Optimization of parameters	1.4.1			█					
Long term test (12M) and Ammonium sulphate production for granulation trials	1.4.1				█	█			
Testing of parameters and production of P-K fertilizer from sewage sludge in pilot scale (20 kg/h, TRL 7) at optimized process parameters.	1.4.2	█	█	█	█				
Granulation trials with N-component (NH4SO4) and PK-component with option for agronomic demonstration.	1.4.2				█	█			
Screening of potential local raw materials and optimisation of parameters in lab scale.	1.4.3	█	█	█					
Pilot trials with 1-2 materials. Optimization of operational parameters.	1.4.3		█	█	█				
Micropollutant removal with activated carbon in test bed.	1.4.3					█	█	█	
Input to assessments and development of exploitation plans for successful innovations	1.4.1-1.4.3							█	█

Updated timetable

- 1.4.1 Commissioning Ammonia Stripping
- 1.4.1 Ammonia Stripping – operation & optimization
- 1.4.2 Lab test (PK-fertilizer) Granulation
- 1.4.2. Pilot trials PK-fertilizer
- 1.4.3 Long-term tests GAC

F formulation G Granulation T thermal treatment

#5. Spernal (UK) Waste Water Treatment Plant

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Energy

Relevant data

Waste water plant serving the town of Redditch
(Birmingham, UK): 92.000 PE

Relevant sectors

Agriculture

Domestic sector

Energy sector

Lead partners

Resource recovery
and innovation centre

WONDERFUL ON TAP SEVERN TRENT

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/spernal/>

Spernal WWTP serves as Severn Trent Water's "Resource Recovery and Innovation Centre" where emerging technologies compatible with a low energy, circular economy approach will be evaluated.

A multi-stream test bed facility was constructed in 2019 and this will incorporate an anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR) to be commissioned in Summer 2020. The AnMBR will also comprise a membrane degassing unit to recover dissolved methane and ion exchange processes to recover nitrogen and phosphorus from the effluent.

AnMBR combines several benefits such as:

- no aeration energy for removal of Chemical and Biological Oxygen Demand (COD/BOD)
- low sludge production and hence reduced downstream sludge treatment costs
- biogas production (production of electricity/heat)
- pathogen and solids free effluent which can be re-used in a number of applications (e.g.: farming and industrial use).

1. General description of the site

Spernal WwTW is the home of Severn Trent's Resource Recovery and Innovation Centre (R2IC). This purpose built facility has been designed and built to undertake large scale wastewater demonstration trials. It is focused on developing and validating technologies and processes that will enable Severn Trent and the wider sector to transition from linear based treatment designs to a more circular economy approach. Opportunities to recover energy, materials and water from wastewater will be maximized.

The R2IC is flexibly designed to host multiple parallel and in-series trials. The AnMBR and tertiary nutrient recovery flowsheet will be installed on the R2IC and will be commissioned in Summer 2020.

**Resource recovery
and innovation centre**

WONDERFUL ON TAP

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Aerial view of the Spernal WWTP

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

- ✓ Nutrient removal and recovery through adsorption or ion exchange technologies

- ✓ AnMBR demonstration in cold climate northern European countries with a membrane degassing unit to recover dissolved methane for water and energy reuse

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Spernal

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 5 Spernal Location: Spernal WWTP	Sub-Task 1.2.3 Multi-stream anaerobic MBR for district-scale reuse applications (Spernal)	Spernal wastewater treatment plant serves as Severn Trent Water's "Urban Strategy Demonstration Site"	Decentralized water treatment by a multi-stream anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR)	TRL 6 → 7	500 m ³ /d (max).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pathogen and solids free effluent which can be re-used in a number of applications (e.g.: farming and industrial use). Low sludge production and hence reduced downstream sludge treatment costs. 	Ongoing. Construction and commissioning of resource recovery innovation center completed in October 2019 AnMBR to be commissioned in next months
	Sub-Task 1.3.3 Decentralized energy recovery and usage from anaerobic MBR (Spernal)		Biogas recovery and energy production throughout two scenarios: i. CHP – electricity & heat (assuming an CHP engine efficiency of 40%) ii. Biogas upgrading and injection to the natural gas network.	TRL 7 → 8	Expected methane yields based on pilot scale work at Cranfield University: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At 20°C - 0.28 L CH₄ / g COD removed At 7°C - 0.19 L CH₄ / g COD removed Assuming 90% removal of COD (from pilot trials): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maximum production: 33m³ CH₄/d Average: 11m³ CH₄/d 	Electricity & heat produced for the two scenarios: i. 44kWh/day and ~ 50kWh heat/d (assuming around 15% losses) ii. 108kWh/d	Ongoing. Linked with AnMBR commissioning and operation
	Sub-Task 1.4.5 Nutrient removal and recovery from AnMBR effluent for local reuse (Spernal)		Nutrient recovery via adsorption / ion exchange (IEX): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> N removal (zeolite column) & N recovery (ammonia stripping or membrane processes) P removal (hybrid anion exchange (HAIX) column) & P recovery (addition of CaOH to the spent regenerant). 	TRL 6 → 7	10 m ³ /d nutrient stripped effluent	Ammonia stripping or membrane processes can be used to produce ammonia solution at 3-5% s or ammonium sulphate, respectively. The regenerant is re-used. Ca ₂ PO ₃ precipitated. The regenerant is re-used.	Ongoing. The recovered nutrients from IEX installed at Cranfield University (move to Spernal Autumn 2020)

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new NextGen solution

5. NextGen solutions

The **anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR)** pilot plant comprises 3 main process units

1. Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor (UASB)
 - Technology provider - Waterleau
 - This will be housed in three 20' shipping containers mounted one on top of the other
 - The UASB will contain granular sludge and have a 3 phase separator at the top of the reactor
 - Most of the solids will be retained in the UASB, the effluent will be directed to the UF membrane and the biogas will be sent to the on-site gas bag
 - Currently delivered to R2IC and undergoing installation and system testing
2. Ultra-filtration (UF) membrane
 - Technology provider – SFC / Trant Engineering
 - This will be housed in two 20' shipping containers
 - The UF membrane will remove any remaining solids from the effluent returning the sludge to the UASB and the effluent to the membrane contactor for degassing
 - Currently delivered to R2IC and undergoing wet testing
3. Membrane contactor for degassing
 - Technology provider – 3M (Membrana)
 - The membrane contactor will remove the dissolved methane from the effluent
 - The methane will be sent to the gas bag and the effluent to the ion exchange nutrient recovery plant
 - Membrana modules on site and system build underway

5. NextGen solutions

Ion Exchange (IEX) nutrient recovery pilot plant

This is a 10 m³/day demonstration scale plant comprises 4 main process units

1. N removal column

- Contains 70L of Zeolite, operated at an empty bed contact time of 10-30 min
- Zeolite needs regeneration when ammonia in the effluent is > 5 mg/L
- Zeolite is regenerated with NaCl or KCl

2. P removal column

- Contains 35L of hybrid anion exchange (HAIX), LayneRT (Layne, USA), Operated at an empty bed contact time of 5-15 min
- HAIX needs regeneration when phosphorus in the effluent is > 2-3 mg/L
- HAIX is regenerated with NaOH

3. N recovery

- Ammonia stripping or membrane processes can be used to produce ammonia solution at 3-5% or ammonium sulphate, respectively. The regenerant is re-used.

4. P recovery

- Addition of CaOH to the spent regenerant, results in the immediate precipitation of CaP that is filtered from the regenerant. The regenerant is re-used.

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures of AnMBR under construction

- AnMBR under construction at R2IC and plant in use forecast for Jan 2021.
- Current status (November 2020)
 - UASB interface pipe work under construction
 - UF membrane installed and wet tested
 - De-gas system civils works complete.

Plan View - Overview

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Granular sludge supplied by Waterleau

Pilot scale UASB reactors

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Pilot scale membrane module

Several hundreds of parallel fibres (1-3 m long with an outside diameter of 0.3-0.5 mm) are wound up around a carrier cartridge

The cartridge has a permeate connection on the top and an air/biogas connection for gas sparging on the bottom

Membrane cartridge is kept suspended inside the membrane tank

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Pilot scale nutrient recovery IEX reactors

Adsorption media used in the columns

mesolite for N recovery

nano-particle impeded IEX beads for P recovery

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the final product

Gas sensors and dissolved methane probe to assist on the measurement of energy production in the AnMBR

Filtering recovered CaP

Recovered ammonium sulphate

6. Operational procedures

- Operational conditions for 70L pilot-plant that will inform the operation of the demonstration anMBR

UASB reactor operation		
HRT	h	8
V_{up}	m/h	0.8

Inoculated with 11 L of granular sludge donated by Waterleau

The membrane module is a SFC C-MEM membrane, composed of polyethylene hollow fibres with a total membrane area of 1.4 m²

Test conditions for the MBR module to complete a critical flux analysis		Flux	SGD _m [*]
		LMH	m ³ m ⁻² h ⁻¹
1	Filtration: 5 min	15	4
	Backwash and gas sparging: 15-30 s		
2	Filtration: 5 min	25	4
	Backwash and gas sparging: 30-60 s		
3	Filtration: 5 min	35	4-6
	Backwash and gas sparging: 30-60 s		

6. Operational procedures

Tools for environmental & economic impacts assessment at Sperial

- Quantitative chemical risk assessment (QCRA)
- Life cycle assessment (LCA)
- Life cycle costing (LCC)
- Cost efficiency analysis (CEA)

7. Specific KPIs (actual vs expected)

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#5 Sernal (UK)	Wastewater treatment and reuse	To increase reuse application for external uses	Volume of water recovered and its use (m ³ /day)	?	500
			Water yield of the system (produced/collected, %)	Not yet measured	
		To enhance water quality: Influent and effluent quality – Rejection rate [%]	Salinity	Not yet measured	?
			BOD	Not yet measured	95% removal
			COD	Not yet measured	90% removal
			SS	Not yet measured	100% removal
			Turbidity	Not yet measured	100% removal
			TN	Not yet measured	60-80% removal
		To reduce the pathogens content of the effluent	E.Coli [CFU/100 ml]	Not yet measured	0
			Legionella spp. [CFU/100 ml]	Not yet measured	0
	Organics removal	Pesticides and pharmaceuticals	Not yet measured	?	
	Energy	Energy recovery – create energy neutral WWTP and export to community (biogas)	Methane yield [m ³ CH ₄ /(kg COD)]	Not yet measured	0.19-0.28
			Quantity of re-used heat (seasonal, m ³ /d)	Not yet measured	11-33
			Energy consumption [kWh/m ³]	Not yet measured	?
			Energy generation [kWh/m ³]	Not yet measured	?
	Materials	To recover nutrients from wastewater effluent	Calcium phosphate (as P, kg/day)	Not yet measured	0.03
			Ammonium sulphate (as N, kg/day)	Not yet measured	0.22

7. Results obtained

JUL-SEPT 2020 (T=18°C)		Characterisation		Removal rates (%)
		<i>Influent</i>	<i>UASB effluent</i>	
COD	mg L ⁻¹	153	56	63
sCOD	mg L ⁻¹	36	29	19
BOD ₅	mg L ⁻¹	65	38	42
TSS	mg L ⁻¹	117	37	68
VSS	mg L ⁻¹	108	31	71
SO ₄	mg L ⁻¹	62	40	35

OCT 2020 – ongoing (T=13°C)		Characterisation		Removal rates (%)
		<i>Influent</i>	<i>UASB effluent</i>	
COD	mg L ⁻¹	195	103	47
sCOD	mg L ⁻¹	44	39	11
BOD ₅	mg L ⁻¹	73	44	40
TSS	mg L ⁻¹	120	40	67
VSS	mg L ⁻¹	103	36	65
SO ₄	mg L ⁻¹	69	43	38

OCT 2020 – ongoing (T=13°C)		
Biogas production	L d ⁻¹	0.6
Dissolved CH ₄ /total CH ₄	%	93.6
Methane yield	L CH ₄ /g COD	0.13

The wastewater has very low strength, making the UASB operation very challenging, as anaerobic processes are favoured by high organic loading rates

The pilot UASB reactor, which mimics the reactor in Sernal, is producing the expected effluent quality

The link to the MBR tank is delayed due to the closing of the pilot site for 4 months and supply chain issues

Data on methane production are sparse and more data points are required

8. Progress and next steps

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
# 5	<p>Spernal, United Kingdom</p> <p>Location: Spernal WWTP</p> <p>Lead Partner: UCRAN</p> <p>Partners Involved: STW</p>	Sub-Task 1.2.3	Decentralized water treatment by a multi-stream anaerobic membrane bioreactor(AnMBR)	Expected delays to site construction and commissioning of the Anaerobic Membrane Bioreactor due to supply chain being effect by COVID related issues, specifically the UASB key component and other supporting equipment.	Working with supply chain to mitigate and minimise COVID-19 delays.

8. Next steps planned

AnMBR Installation

	End date
WATERLEAU (Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor)	
Wet testing of UASB	16 Nov 2020
Commissioning and start up	20 Jan 2021
Trant (Ultra-filtration membrane)	
Wet testing of UF membrane	16 Nov 2020
Commissioning and start up	20 Jan 2021
3M (Membrane degassing system)	
Wet testing of Degas system	08 Jan 2021
Commissioning of 3M equipment	28 Jan 2021
ANMBR	
Plant in Use	28 Jan 2020

8. Next steps planned: from November 2020 (M29) on

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Task description	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40
WATERLEAU (Upflow anaerobic sludge blanket reactor)												
Wet testing of UASB	■											
Commissioning and start up			■									
Trant (Ultra-filtration membrane)												
Wet testing of UF membrane	■											
Commissioning and start up			■									
3M (Membrane degassing system)												
Wet testing of Degas system			■									
Commissioning of 3M equipment			■									
ANMBR												
Plant in Use												■

8. Next steps Updated timetable

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Task description	Task	2018	2019		2020		2021		2022
		M1-M6	M7-M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-M48
Detailed design of Anaerobic MBR (AnMBR). Appoint contractor	1.2.3 1.3.3	█							
Construction, commissioning and hand-over of AnMBR demonstrator	1.2.3 1.3.3		█						
Start-up and optimization of individual components – acclimatisation of Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (USAB), optimization of membrane filtration system, optimization of membrane degas unit	1.2.3						█		
	1.3.3								
Installation and commissioning of IEX columns for nitrogen and phosphorus recovery from the AnMBR effluent	1.4.5						█		
Optimisation and trouble-shooting of process flowsheet	1.2.3							█	
Operation of IEX columns for nitrogen and phosphorus recovery from the AnMBR effluent	1.4.5							█	
Operation of AnMBR demonstrator and evaluation of performance under static and dynamic flow and load conditions. Confirmation of the optimal design and operating parameters.	1.2.3							█	
Assessment of results, delivery of a comprehensive energy balance and cost benefit assessment	1.2.3								█

#6. La Trappe (NL)

La Trappe brewery

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Relevant data

Capacity: ~360 m³/day (10,000 PE)

Footprint: 847m²

Value: Water circularity showcase

Relevant sectors

Beverage industry

Municipal sector

Space industry

Lead partners

The Koningshoeven BioMakery is a biological wastewater treatment system based on modular and functional reactor- based ecological engineering.

Based upon the principle of water-based urban circularity, where energy, food, and waste systems are built around a regenerative and sustainable water cycle.

Powered by Metabolic Network Reactor (MNR) technology, which uses 2-3,000 different species of organisms ranging from bacteria to higher level organisms such as plants.

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/la-trappe/>

1. General description of the site

- ✓ The Koningshoeven BioMakery is fully integrated into the historical monument of the Koningshoeven Trappist Abbey and Brewery. The facility treats industrial wastewater from the brewery and municipal wastewater from the Abbey and Visitor center.
- ✓ The industrial wastewater is reused at the abbey for irrigation of the abbey grounds and plant nurseries. It is a long term goal to reuse the industrial wastewater for bottle rinsing within the brewery.

AE: Aerobic Zone
AX: Anoxic Zone

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

<Current situation>

Brewery water treatment line

Estimated Influent flow 360 m³/d

MNR1 AE MNR2 AE MNR3 AE MNR4 AE MNR5 AE MNR6 AE MNR7 AE MNR8 AE

MNR00 AE

An existing empty tank was transformed into an aerated reactor for the capacity increase of the brewery line.

Brewery water

- High COD
- Fluctuating pH
- Cleaning chemicals

Municipal water treatment line

Estimated Influent flow 18 m³/d

MNR1 AX/AE MNR2 AE

FeCl₃ dosage

Notes:

MNR1 – MNR4 were built so that they can be run as optional anoxic reactors, should the incoming wastewater have high levels of nitrogen. Currently, they are running as aerated reactors.
The Influent flow rates have been highly variable due to Covid19. Production at the brewery was affected and the visitor center was temporarily closed.

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Brewery water

320 m³/day

High COD

Fluctuating pH

Cleaning chemicals

and

Municipal Water

15-18m³/day

Fluctuating N

> 150000 visitors a year

Unknown:
pathogens & OMP

- ✓ Different streams require a custom-made approach. As a consequence of the potential presence of pathogens and outer membrane proteins (OMPs) in the municipal water, brewery water is safer to start with.

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

- ✓ Combine Metabolic Network Reactor (MNR) and membranes for nutrient and water recovery for fit-for-use industrial use such as irrigation, bottlewashing or make up water for beer production

- ✓ Use “Bio-makery” for water reuse in decentralized areas

- ✓ Carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus recovery, with nutrients removed from the water converted into fertilizer used to produce plant or microbial protein

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

La Trappe

- Nitrogen recovery
- Phosphorus recovery
- Composting
- Granulated Activated Carbon (GAC) production

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 6 La Trappe Location: La Trappe Brewery	Sub-Task 1.2.6 Production of fit-for-purpose water in La Trappe	La Trappe brewery wastewater treatment plant	Metabolic Network Reactor (MNR - plant root enhanced fixed bed bioreactor) + MELiSSA Advanced Separation systems (MF/RO) to produce fit-for-purpose water	MNR - plant root enhanced fixed bed bioreactor (TRL 7 → 9) + NF/RO/ED to produce fit-for-purpose water (TRL 4 → 6)	NF/UF 150 L/h and RO 100 L/h MELiSSA inspired fit-for-purpose is smaller capacity.	Recovery of regenerated effluent fit-for-use such as irrigation, bottle washing or make up water for beer production	The MNR water treatment facility is fully operational. However, Covid19 continues to impact operations: operators were sick with the virus, affecting commissioning activities and sampling; the capacity continues to fluctuate due to production variations at the brewery and visitor center; travel restrictions affect fine-tuning of the facility, and integration of pilot technologies to the site. Set-up of the NextGen pilot systems, and preliminary tasks are currently taking place independently.
	Sub-task 1.4.4. Protein production in Bio-Makeries		Use of photobioreactor and “Bio-makery” (utilization of axenic and mixed native species of “Spirulina” A. platensis in real life conditions): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C recovery • N recovery • P recovery 	TRL 4 → 6	60L/d	Fertilizer Used in fish fodder or directly as human food	Due to the available process water quality, it was decided to focus on photoheterotrophic compartment using PnSB instead of photoautotrophic Spirulina. An open pond reactor has been developed inspired by MELISSA CII compartment. Off-site tests using the La Trappe process water were successful. There were several delays for the onsite tests, but the system has been repaired and is back in operation after the corona crisis.

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new NextGen solution

Water discharged to the nearby canal, maintaining the local water cycle, preventing drought in the area. Water is also used for irrigation.

5. NextGen solutions

Scenario studies best custom-made solution for brewery water

Inspired by MELiSSA C2, Axenic cultivation of *R. Rubrum*

Inspired by Concordia MELiSSA membrane system running at research station on Antarctica

Hypothesis 1: Safe conversion of COD to mixed culture PnSB, reduces COD load on MNR and increases MNR capacity

Hypothesis 2: Effluent microfiltration suitable for potable water production

5. NextGen solutions

Mass balance custom-made solution for brewery water

Real brewery Influent characteristics used for simulations

For robustness of calculation brewery flow was oversized

Hypothesis 1: Mass balance supports hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 2: Mass balance supports hypothesis 2, but scaling should be paid attention to

5. NextGen solutions

MELiSSA: Inspiration by Concordia Research Station

French/Italian research station on Antarctica

- Aim to not contaminate pristine environment
 - 90%+ recycling of grey water for 10-15 overwintering scientists
 - Semi-autonomous operation for 8 years
 - Very robust: limited maintenance required

© 2020, SEMiLLA IPStar

5. NextGen solutions

MELiSSA inspiration: WTUB

De Paepe et al. (2018);
Lindeboom et al. (2020)

5. NextGen solutions

MELiSSA inspiration: WTUB

All given the energy that is available

Net Water Use

Slope =
Water use * (1-η)

robustness
initial capital
expenses

mass spares
mass hardware

**Data adapted from J

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new Nextgen solution

- MELiSSA Separation systems offline tests

5L Raw brewery water send to France

Ultrafiltration

Reverse Osmosis

Potable water quality reached

Larger pilot experiment is being planned

Preliminary tests successfully performed by MELiSSA/SEMiLLA IPStar partner Firmus

<http://www.fgwrs.mc/en/homepage/>

5. NextGen solutions

Final Scheme of the new NextGen solution

© 2020, SEMiLLA IPStar

5. NextGen solutions

Local solution to COVID challenges

Collaboration started with Jotem waterbehandeling B.V.

- Construction of WTUB inspired systems on-going
 - Site Tests starting in december and will remain in operation till may next year
 - Scenario 1: Brewery effluent
 - Scenario 2: Municipal effluent
 - Both scenarios: reuse quality of permeate (QMRA and QCRA) and concentrate quality for purple bacteria

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new Nextgen solution

➤ Photobioreactor technology

Operating Axenic conditions reactor not financially realistic for waste materials

MELiSSA Purple Bacteria Reactor

(axenic conditions)

Translated into terrestrial open pond application in co-operation with MELiSSA UAntwerp partner

Hybrid futuristic reactor

Designed by TUDelft BSc minor Environmental Engineering students

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Photobioreactor technology

↑ Flask cultivation of PnSB under different brewery water conditions @ 2019
UAntwerp

→ Radu Giurgiu and Giorgio Gardella preparing PnSB pond reactor at La Trappe premises 26-2-2020

5. NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Photobioreactor technology on La Trappe site

6. Operational procedure brewery line

6.1 Combine MNR and MELiSSA advanced separation technologies

Water type	COD	Ammonium	TN	TP	TSS	Chloride	Sulphate
MNR	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly	Weekly

Water type	TSS	FCU	Chloride	Turbidity	TP	Total COD	TN	EC
Lab separation experiment	Influent/Concentrate permeate	Twice/ week	Influent/Concentrate permeate	Potable water parameters				
La Trappe	Every other day	QMRA	weekly	Twice per week	Twice per week	Daily	Twice per week	online

6.2 Photobioreactor technology

Water type	TDS	FCU	Suspended solids	Turbidity	TP	Total COD	TN	Other
Lab experiments	Influent effluent	N/A	Daily	Occasionally	Daily	Daily	Daily	
La Trappe site	TBD	TBD	Daily (for growth)	Occasionally (when water is discharged)	Twice / week	Twice / week	Twice / week	Sulphuric acid dosage in brewery causes H ₂ S emission

6. Operational procedures

Tools in WP5 to assess circular elements in the La Trappe case (under development and being tested)

- Life cycle assessment (LCA)
- Life cycle costing (LCC)
- Cost efficiency analysis (CEA)

7. Specific KPIs

- MNR Water quality analysis

Case study	Topic	Objectives		Key Parameters	Influent Range (mg/l)	Discharge Limits (mg/l)	Effluent Range (mg/l)
#6 La Trappe (NL)	Water	Successful operation of brewery MNR	Effluent is fit for irrigation use / aquifer recharge.	COD	453 – 3829	125	62 – 427
				Ammonium	0.08 – 4.6	1	0.01 – 8.3
				TN	4.9 – 47	10	4.8 – 24.1
				TP	4.5 – 26.1	0.3	1.8 – 17.8
				TSS	No Data	2	No Data
				Chloride	43 – 110	60	60 – 80
				Sulphate	20 – 103	60	62 – 159

Note: The MNR on the brewery line demonstrated the ability to reduce most important water quality parameters below discharge limits under stable influent conditions. However, due to a highly variable influent and operational difficulties stemming from Covid19, the system is not yet stable and does not meet the discharge limits consistently.

Case study	Topic	Objectives		Key Parameter Indicators (KPIs)	Current value	Expected value
#6 La Trappe (NL)	Water	Successful operation of brewery MNR	Water recovery for fit-for-use (irrigation & aquifer recharge)	Water yield of the system (produced / collected, %)	NS	90-95%
			Energy consumption (kWh/m ³ produced)		NS	200
		Couple MELiSSA Advanced separation to the brewery line of the MNR	Influent and effluent quality (rejection rate, %)	TDS/ EC (µS/cm)	NS	500
				NO ₃	NS	50-60%
				COD	NS	90%
	Materials	To recover N from the NF/RO concentrate using MELiSSA Photobioreactor technology		TOC	NS	90%
				Carbon and N recovery rate [%]	NS	60% (C), 100% (N)

NS: Not Specified

7. Results obtained

Task 1.4.4. Protein production in Bio-Makeries

PFD and Matlab model of the pilot plant

- Phase frequency detector (PFD) by Uantwerp and Matlab model in collaboration with TUDelft and U Antwerpen

7. Results obtained

Task 1.4.4. Protein production in Bio-Makeries

Photobioreactor technology on La Trappe site

7. Results obtained

- The MNR on the brewery line **demonstrated the ability to reduce most important water quality parameters** below discharge limits under stable influent conditions. However, the MNR system was not originally designed to handle the large fluctuations the system has endured during the covid19 crisis.
- Two main problems were encountered.
 - i. **Extreme influent ranges** coming from the brewery.
 - ii. **Operational management issues:** the two system operators became sick with Covid19; and system adjustments were needed to address the extreme conditions.
- **Future-proofing.** In future designs, the experiences gained from running the MNR system under extreme conditions, will help improve MNR system tolerance design. The adjustments at the La Trappe facility will help stabilize the system, ensuring that the effluent will consistently meet the discharge limits.

7. Results obtained

- Off-site test membrane system successful on raw brewery water
- Off-site Purple bacteria tests using the La Trappe brewery water were successful and showed high growth potential for PnSB.
- Modeling supported mixed culture growth hypothesis on La Trappe brewery water
- Reactor at La Trappe is turning purple with fluctuating influent conditions!

8. Progress and next steps

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#6	<p>La Trappe, Netherlands Location: La Trappe factory Lead Partner: IPSTAR Partners involved: BIOPOL, WDD</p>	Sub-Task 1.2.6	<p>Metabolic Network Reactor (MNR - plant root enhanced fixed bed bioreactor) + MELiSSA Advanced Separation systems (MF/RO) to produce fit-for-purpose water</p>	<p>Both the brewery line and the municipal line have been restarted. The visitor center at the abbey re-opened at the beginning of June. Effluent testing and analysis has also begun again. Due to Covid19, Biopolus can not travel to the abbey to help with system fine-tuning. Biopolus is working (on-line) with the operators to manage the extremes, so that the system can be stabilized.</p> <p>The MELiSSA systems are being prepared separately, and will be integrated into the MNR system depending on the Covid19 situation and the steps that can be taken with Covid19 restrictions in place.</p>	<p>Monthly online meetings are on-going. Critical paths have been discussed and identified in order to prioritize next steps. Biopolus is working with the MNR system operators and the brewery to stabilize the brewery effluent, so that the extreme fluctuations do not affect MNR biology. Biopolus is working to help the local operators cope with operational changes. System fine-tuning is also taking place.</p> <p>A new solution has been prepared that could replace the MELiSSA pilot system that is currently located in France. It still follows the approach as described in recently accepted manuscript on MELiSSA inspired shower water treatment using UF/NF and RO.</p> <p>In the new schedule the system could be tested at a capacity of ~100 L/h from end of october/beginning of november onwards, assuming MNR effluent quality remains stable</p>

8. Progress and next steps

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Delay	Contingency plan
#6	<p>La Trappe, Netherlands Location: La Trappe factory Lead Partner: IPSTAR Partners involved: BIOPOL, WDD</p>	Sub-Task 1.4.4	<p>Use of photobioreactor and “Bio-makery” (use of axenic and mixed native species of “Spirulina” A. platensis in real life conditions): C recovery, N recovery</p>	<p>The SEMiLLA demonstration activities of the purple bacteria reactor on-site have been paused. Several pieces of equipment are at suppliers and are delayed. Moreover, the key personal for operation of these reactors live in Belgium and are not allowed to visit the site. Just prior to the outbreak Ralph Lindeboom visited their MELiSSA partner in France. They foresee delays in planning the transport of the equipment to the Netherlands, as the situation in France is more severe than in Netherlands and the French operator would be required. It is unclear when and if transporting this equipment will still be feasible in the short/mid term.</p>	<p>Looking at alternative scenarios, in which they can transport brewery water to France for additional remote membrane tests and / or using the evaporator based containerized system (ISS inspired) that they have as a demonstration setup available in the Netherlands. Due to the available process water quality, it was decided to focus on photoheterotrophic compartment using PnSB instead of photoautotrophic Spirulina. An open pond reactor has been developed inspired by MELISSA CII compartment. Off-site tests using the La Trappe process water were succesful and showed high growth potential for PnSB. There were several delays for the onsite tests, but the system has been repaired and is back in operation after the corona crisis.</p>

8. Next steps planned

Planned timetable

La Trappe (NL)	Identify reuse possibilities (fit-for-purpose) at La Trappe, and determine exact water quality requirements	1.2.6	Yellow						
	Adapt existing grey water treatment unit (GWTU) to La Trappe real-life conditions by removing non-essential elements	1.2.6		Blue					
	Operation of pilot and evaluate performance of water quality and quantity that can be generated using different GWTU configurations	1.2.6			Green				
	Design and build photobioreactor according to MELiSSA specifications	1.4.4			Green				
	Cultivate Spirulina on real life effluent and test quality	1.4.4				Green			
	Operate pilot reactor on site	1.4.4					Green		
	Evaluate results of overall La Trappe project	1.4.4							Yellow

Objective	Scale (Full scale / Pilot scale / Theoretical study)	Semester 2 2019	Quarter 3 2020	Quarter 4 2020
Municipal MNR	Full scale	Not operational.	System online, recommissioning started.	System online, recommissioning in progress.
Couple MELiSSA Grey Water Treatment to MNR brewery effluent	Pilot scale	Effluent was not available, so used raw brewery water for preliminary tests off-site. Based on these tuning of equipment can be done	Planning onsite experiment using raw brewery water	Operation on effluent MNR starts beginning of december.
Reduce nitrogen load on municipal MNR by recovering N COD using PnSBTechnology	Lab Bench Scale / Pilot scale	Lab scale has been performed	Lab-scale system moved to La Trappe.	Long term stability purple bacteria

Delays:

*2019 February – May: Commissioning of the brewery line.

*2019 May – October: MNR system was shut down for reconstruction. Bottlenecks posed by the aeration system required adjustments to the system. The system was adapted and reconstructed to address the aeration problem, and to increase the overall capacity of the brewery line for the planned brewery expansion.

*2019 November – 2020 March: Re-commissioning of the brewery line. The brewery line should be up and running by the end of March.

*2020 Covid19 delays. Just as the brewery line was restarted and stabilizing, the brewery was shut down due to Covid19. The visitor center was also closed, and the entire municipal line was shut down. Once the brewery operations restarted and then ramped up and the visitor center reopened, the system needed to be re-stabilized. The extreme changes in system influent has affected final system stabilization, which is still on-going.

8. Next steps planned: from November 2020 on

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Task description	Task	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	
Industrial MNR (work to get (keep) Municipal MNR online if wastewater flow is sufficient and consistent)		Full-scale												
Couple MELiSSA Grey Water Treatment to MNR brewery effluent			Pilot-scale											
Reduce nitrogen load on municipal MNR by recovering N COD using PnSBTechnology		Theoretical work												

Delays:

*2019 February – May: Commissioning of the brewery line.

*2019 May – October: MNR system was shut down for reconstruction. Bottlenecks posed by the aeration system required adjustments to the system. The system was adapted and reconstructed to address the aeration problem, and to increase the overall capacity of the brewery line for the planned brewery expansion.

*2019 November – 2020 March: Re-commissioning of the brewery line. The brewery line should be up and running by the end of March.

*2020 Covid19 delays. Just as the brewery line was restarted and stabilizing, the brewery was shut down due to Covid19. The visitor center was also closed, and the entire municipal line was shut down. Once the brewery operations restarted and then ramped up and the visitor center reopened, the system needed to be re-stabilized. The extreme changes in system influent has affected final system stabilization, which is still on-going.

8. Next steps

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Planned timetable

La Trappe (NL)	Identify reuse possibilities (fit-for-purpose) at La Trappe, and determine exact water quality requirements	1.2.6	Full-scale															
	Adapt existing grey water treatment unit (GWTU) to La Trappe real-life conditions by removing non-essential elements	1.2.6		Full-scale														
	Operation of pilot and evaluate performance of water quality and quantity that can be generated using different GWTU configurations	1.2.6			Pilot-scale													
	Design and build photobioreactor according to MELISSA specifications	1.4.4			Pilot-scale													
	Cultivate Spirulina on real life effluent and test quality	1.4.4				Pilot-scale												
	Operate pilot reactor on site	1.4.4							Pilot-scale									
	Evaluate results of overall La Trappe project	1.4.4																Full-scale

Updated timetable

Task description	Task	2019		2020		2021		2022
		M7-M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-M48
Stabilize operation of full scale MNR	1.2.6	Full-scale						
Off line tests (GWTU)	1.2.6			Pilot-scale				
Adapt GWTU by removing non-essential elements (RO)	1.2.6				Full-scale			
Operation of MELISSA inspired GWTU	1.2.6					Pilot-scale		
Cultivate PNSB on real effluent and test growth performance	1.4.4	Pilot-scale						
Design and build photo bioreactor according to MELISSA and site conditions	1.4.4	Full-scale			Full-scale			
Operate Purple pilot on site (raw effluent)	1.4.4			Pilot-scale				
Operate improved Purple pilot onsite (selected effluent)	1.4.4				Pilot-scale			
Evaluate results of overall process							Full-scale	

#7 Gotland

Sweden

Circular solutions for

Water

Relevant data

Storsudred testbed area: 14 000 ha

Habitants during winter: 900

Habitants during summer : 1800

Tourists per year: 300 000

Relevant sectors

Tourist
industry

Municipal
sector

Water
sector

Lead partners

Introduction to the demo case: <https://nextgenwater.eu/gotland/>

1. General description of the site

In recent years, the island of Gotland has experienced a severe water crisis, negatively affecting tourism and small-scale industries.

Water shortages hinder economic development due to strict regulations for building of new houses and the start-up of new business that consume water.

A national funded testbed (1,5M€ investment + 1,5M€ for evaluation and development) in the water sector is currently active in southern Gotland, the peninsula Storsudret.

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Treated waste water discharged to the Baltic sea

Burgsvik WWTP

Burgsvik

Portable water from north of Gotland by pipeline

4/5 of the volume to the WwTP is rainwater. The sewage serves as rainwater harvesting system

Testbed Storsudret

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

- Water supply systems:
- One municipal water supply system for half of the population at Storsudret. The rest of the inhabitants have their own wells.
- Feed by water from the central part of the island Gotland through a pipeline fed by desalinated water. It is expected that the testbed will provide enough water, so a second desalination plant can be avoided.
- WW are transported 40 km to central Gotland

NextGen proposal

- A Testbed is currently under development in southern peninsula called Storsudret (annual water consumption of 300,000 m³). It's an integrated system based on :
- Rainwater harvesting from drainage ditches and artificial surface water dams or automatic controlled/balanced accumulation in natural lake
- Artificial infiltration to groundwater (if necessary)
- Groundwater dams for subsurface water storage
- Wastewater reuse
- Climate efficient energy based on solar energy

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Water

- **Rainwater harvesting using automatic floodgates** to replenish aquifers and monitoring of aquifer levels
- **Decentralized membrane treatment of raw wastewater** to reduce volumes treated at the central WWTP
- **Climate efficient wastewater reuse powered by solar energy** to overcome carbon footprint drawbacks
- **Optimized membrane filtration** for producing drinkable water from challenging surface water
- **Storage of water** in subsurface dams

Automatic floodgate

Subsurface dams

Storsudret with on-line sensors for water measurement and control

reclaimed waste water

Solar energy for climate efficient water reuse

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB)

Gotland

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
#7. Gotland, Sweden	Sub-Task 1.2.1	“Import” of portable water from central Gotland. Conventional WWTP.	Decentralized membrane treatment of raw sewage mixed with rainwater (sedimentation – grid – discfilter – ultrafiltration – reverse osmosis – UV)	TRL 5 → 7	1 m ³ /h	Regenerated effluent for being reused (e.g. used for potable water)	Pilot off-site tests finished. The pilots under construction. The WWTP rebuilt and ready for piloting.
	Location: southern Gotland, the peninsula Storsudret. Lead Partner: IVL Partners: KWR, PZH, RoG	Sub-Task 1.2.1	“Import” of portable water from central Gotland. Conventional WWTP.	Rainwater harvesting from drainage ditches, natural ponds or artificial surface water dams. Drainage ditches with IoT technology for flow and water levels measuring and control	TRL 5 → 7	Estimated : 100,000 m ³ /year*	Water to natural ponds and artificial dams for infiltration. IoT technology for measuring the flow, ground water level and surface water level every 10-30 min.

5. NextGen solutions

5. NextGen solutions

5.1. Decentralised membrane treatment powered by solar energy

- Storsudret has a perfect position to demonstrate the benefit of a decentralised membrane treatment system.
- Gotland being one of the places with the most sun hours a year in Sweden together with the water shortages during summer gives the perfect demonstration site for membrane treatment powered by solar energy.
- Recovering water close to the source where it is needed provides several benefits. Water can be provided in areas of severe water shortage. Both investment and operation cost for pipes and pumping are decreased. A more concentrated waste stream enable better energy and resource efficiency for wastewater treatment.
- A combination of conventional filtration and membrane technology recover water from the municipal wastewater that are then mixed with the harvested rainwater to produce drinking water for the region.

5. NextGen solutions

5.2. Drainage ditches with IoT for flow and water levels control

Measurement of precipitation

Ground water levels

Surface level in lake

Installation of real-time sensors

Calibration of water flow in ditches

Water flow in ditches

Water flow in ditches

5. NextGen solutions

5.2. Drainage ditches with IoT for flow and water levels control

The storage of water is the main challenge

- Storsudret has a large number of ditches preventing farmer land from being overflowed during springtime
- A rain sampler, sensors in ditches, ground water and a lake has IoT technology installed measuring rain volume flow, ground water level and surface water level every 10-30 min.
- The real time monitoring will be used for control of a flood gate to balance the water in the Storsudret test bed.

1 300 000 m³ / year
flows out to the sea

	Dec 18	Jan 19	Feb 19	Mar 19	Apr 19	Maj 19	Jun 19
SY1	27435	54852	165519	159869	27492	11029	0
SY2	46244	125594	314171	354353	30352	2894	0
PY1	19640	93840	635813	559909	75777	38906	33590

Ground water level

Rain per day

5. NextGen solutions

5.3. Controlled neutral ponds dams for storage

To pilot WTP for production of 60 000 m³ drinking water quality

Water balance established but the automatic floodgate is foreseen to have delays of 9 – 12 months before testing the system (summer 2021).

5. NextGen solutions

5.4. Groundwater dams for subsurface water storage

- Natural or artificial "under ground ponds/dams" are discovered and evaluated by novel methods and will be used to store water.
- Damme water (if necessary) will be infiltrated to ground, pumped out for potential use as potable water for new houses.

Soil depths by georadar

Naturally occurring sub surface dams discovered by SkyTM (right figure)

6. Operational procedures

Operational and analytical parameters

Membrane treatment

- Recovered water quality
 - Since water is recovered for drinking water quality purposes one of the main parameters are that drinking water regulations can be obtained.
- Yield
 - Along with the water quality the recovery of each process is important to determine the overall system feasibility.
- Energy consumption
 - The energy consumption for the recovery system will be compared to the system with seawater desalination, pumping and centralized wastewater treatment plant.

6. Operational procedures

Operational and analytical parameters

Rainwater harvesting and treatment by ultrafiltration

- Collected water quality
 - Since water collected is for drinking water purposes one of the main parameters are that drinking water regulations can be obtained.
- Yield
 - Along with the water quality the produced volume is important to determine the overall system feasibility.
- Energy consumption
 - The energy consumption for the water production system will be compared to the system with seawater desalination, pumping and centralized wastewater treatment plant.

6. Operational procedures

Tools for environmental & economic impacts assessment at Gotland (WP2)

- Life cycle costing
- Cost efficiency analysis
- Hydroptim system design of water supply
- This information will be collected in D2.2

7. Results and specific KPIs (actual vs expected)

7.1. Specific KPIs

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#7 Gotland (SE)	Wastewater treatment and reuse	To obtain regenerated water for being used as potable water	Water yield of the system [% of regenerated water produced] water	0	10%
			Water quality - Removal yield [%] of the following parameters (outlet vs inlet): conductivity, COD, ammonia,		80, 95, 75
	Rainwater harvesting	Rainwater harvesting and storage in surface dams & lake.	Collection capacity [m ³ /year]		100 000
	Aquifer storage	Rainwater and lake water for UF treatment	Pilot capacity [m ³ /year]		60 000
			Water quality - Removal yield [%] of the following parameters (outlet vs inlet): metals, conductivity, color, COD, some anions and <i>E.coli</i> .		80, 10, 50, 80, 10, 99
Energy	Use of solar panels to minimize electricity consumption during wastewater reuse (summer)	Electricity consumption [kWh/m ³ regenerated water]	3		

7. Results

7.2. Decentralized membrane treatment

Off-site tests

Water quality

Parameter	Removal (%)
NH ₄ ⁺	90%
COD	88%
Conductivity	99%
TSS (No filter)	0%
TSS (20 μ-filter)	40%
TSS (30 μ-filter)	23%
TSS (150 μ-filter)	6%

Water recovery yield

Parameter	Value
Concentration Factor (CF) for the UF	10-25
Concentration Factor (CF) for the RO	7.3
Global CF	4.5 – 5.8
Water recovery	78 – 83%

Energy consumption

- The main challenge so far is to **reduce energy consumption** in the ultrafiltration unit
- Back-pulsing, chemicals, crossflow rate, pore size and pre-filtration has been investigated to optimize operation.
- The higher energy consumption of ultrafiltration of untreated wastewater could be compensated by:
 - reduced energy for long-distance pumping of wastewater and drinking water,
 - higher energy and resource yield in the wastewater treatment,
 - lower energy consumption for drinking water production.

Off-site tests finalized. Pilot under construction. Pilot operation: March 2021

7. Results

7.3. Rain water harvesting

- The average precipitation on Storsudret is ca 600 mm/year (data from regional weather station, Hoburgen year 1961-1990).
- Metals have been measured in both surface and ground water as well as sediment in order to detect signs of pollution, to understand the quality of raw water and the amount of treatment needed before transformation to drinking water.
- Sampled quality parameters are compared to national assessment evaluation tool for the purpose to make uniform classifications of ground water in Sweden. Values relate to effects on health, environment and technical installations and should be reviewed as a starting point for risk assessment

Water quality

Lake

- Results show higher concentrations of Ca, Na, Mg and Cl which is expected consequences from the closeness to the sea and limestone bedrock (all results in table 1-2). At one occasion in late summer levels of NH₄ and bacteria were very high 0.58 mgN/l and >5000 cfu/ml respectively but can be explained by grazing cattle with availability to the lake. Also, TOC were high at one sampling occasion during summer 33 mg/l.

Ground water

- Results from sampling of ground water in areas with planned subsurface dams show high concentrations of Fe, Mn, Ni and As all associated to bedrock material

Sediments

- Sediment content have been analyzed and show nothing abnormal but very high content of Ca as expected from limestone bedrock. Sediment thickness varies between one to almost three meters

- Water volumes in ditches, lake, rain and ground have been on-line monitored
- MY3 are inflow of water into lake Mjölhatteträsk and are high during late autumn, spring and highest during winter but very low during summer. The outflow from the lake to the sea is limited by a threshold. Maximum volume to be stored in lake 100 000 m³ (present conditions) which together with reused volume of wastewater, c. 25 000 m³.

Inflow and outflow of water to lake Mjölhatteträsk plotted with precipitation data. IoT-sensors installed at MY3 and MY1.

7. Results

7.4. Drainage ditches with IoT for flow and water levels control

- Storsudret has a large number of ditches preventing farmer land from being overflowed during springtime
- A water and a lake has IoT technology installed measuring rain volume flow, ground water level and surface water level **every 10-30 min rain sampler, sensors in ditches, ground.**
- The real time monitoring will be used for control of a flood gate to balance the water in the Storsudret test bed.

1 300 000 m³ / year flows out to the sea

Ground water level

Rain per day

7. Results

7.5. Controlled neutral ponds dams for storage

Water quality

Contaminants analysed in surface water, ground water and sediments to design the treatment system for producing drinking water.

Lake

- Results show higher concentrations of Ca, Na, Mg and Cl which is expected consequences from the closeness to the sea and limestone bedrock.
- At one occasion in late summer levels of NH₄, TOC and bacteria were high, explained by grazing cattle with availability to the lake.
- **Membrane filtration will remove bacteria's and organic substances. NH₄ must be controlled.**

Ground water

- Results from sampling of ground water in areas with planned subsurface dams show high concentrations of Fe, Mn, Ni and As all associated to bedrock material. **Water treatment might be necessary** for drinking purposes.

Sediments

- Sediment content have been analyzed and show nothing abnormal but very high content of Ca as expected from limestone bedrock. Sediment thickness varies between one to almost three meters and **removal of sediment could result in larger capacity** for water storage.

Automatic floodgate and membrane filtration spring 2021

Water quantity

- The average precipitation on Storsudret is ca 600 mm/year.
- Water volumes in ditches, lake, rain and ground have been on-line monitored.
- The resulting water balance shows that **100 000 m³ could be stored** in the lake without (increasing the surface level) if outlet is hindered by an automatic floodgate.

Inflow and outflow of water to lake Mjölhatteträsk plotted with precipitation data. IoT-sensors installed at MY3 and MY1.

7. Results

7.6. Groundwater dams for subsurface water storage

Depressions in rock – SkyTM

- Detailed investigation is being finalized in December 2020
- If positive: Large scale capacity test in January 2021

8. Progress and next steps planned

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#7	Gotland	Sub-Task 1.2.1	Decentralized membrane treatment of raw sewage mixed with rainwater (sedimentation – grid – disc filter – ultrafiltration – reverse osmosis – UV)	The off-site tests has been extended to find the optimal conditions for the design of the pilot equipment. The construction of the pilots has minor delays due to the Covid-19 situation.	The delay will be less than a half year so this will not have an important impact to the task.
		Sub-Task 1.2.1	Rainwater harvesting from drainage ditches, natural ponds and artificial surface water dams. Drainage ditches with IoT technology for flow and water levels measuring and control.	The on-site installation of the smart real time measuring was carried out 2018-2019. The control for the automatic floodgates were planned for springtime-summer 2020. Due to the Covid-19 situation this has not been possible. The installation can be problematic during winter and if the installation is hindered there might be a delay to springtime 2021.	It will be a slightly shorter evaluation period for the collection of water but this will not have an important impact to the task. The real time monitoring is up and running and collects the important data. New bore holes have been established for ground water measurements and soil evaluation and large-scale tests will be carried out in December or January.

8. Progress and next steps planned

Next steps planned

Rainwater harvesting

- During autumn 2020 installation of wells (most already established) and one larger for performing larger scale capacity test by pumping of underground stored water.
- Building a permanent , automatic hatche at outflow of lake during spring 2021. Testing of real time control to keep the raise lake level instead of flushing out to the sea.

WWTP

- Evaluation of optimal conditions by oof-site tests finished and the design of the pilot- and demonstration plant have been set.
- Equipment is under construction and will be installed early 2021 (February-April) at the rebuilt WWTP in Burgsvik.

#8. Athens

Greece

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Energy

Relevant data

9000 m³ water reused/ year

5000 kg compost production/ year

8700 kWh thermal energy recovery/ year

Relevant sectors

Water treatment

Horticulture

Energy

Lead partner:

National
Technical
University of
Athens

Other partners:

BIOPOLUS
The Living Technology Alliance

CHEMITEC
Water and Environmental Technologies

CITY OF
ATHENS

EYDAP

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/athens/>

1. General description of the site

Urban Tree Nursery

- part of the Goudi Park, an area in the process of becoming the key metropolitan park of the capital.
- 4 ha of vegetation
- supplier of plant material for urban parks and green spaces in Athens
- uses potable water from EYDAP for irrigation
- pruning waste is accumulated in the nursery, not treated, partly transferred in Athens landfill

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Athens Tree Nursery current situation

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

	Objectives
Water	Produce water from urban wastewater with a sewer mining modular unit for urban green irrigation and other non-potable uses at the point of demand - about 25m³/day (wastewater treatment with membrane bioreactor and disinfection)
Energy	Implement thermal energy recovery flexible solutions - about 10kW (thermal energy will be recovered using heat exchangers and heat pumps systems to cover technology processes as well as thermal needs of the nursery e.g. buildings, greenhouses)
Materials	Produce compost-based eco-engineered growing media products - about 100 Kg/week (organic materials of pruning waste and wastewater sludge will produce a compost to be reused as onsite fertilizer)

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Athens

4. Summary Table: water & energy

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 2 Athens (EL) Location: Urban tree nursery in the Goudi Park	Sub-Task 1.2.4 Mobile wastewater treatment for decentralized reuse applications	Use of potable water for irrigation of trees	Sewer Mining Modular unit (MBR & UV disinfection) for the production of regenerated water	TRL 6 → 8	25 m ³ /d	Regenerated water for urban green irrigation and other non-potable uses at the point of demand	Ongoing. The Sewer Mining unit has been installed in the site and has been tested with clean water. The pumping station has been installed in the site and is connected to the SM in order to proceed with the full operation of the wastewater treatment unit.
	Sub-Task 1.3.4 Flexible decentralized energy recovery	Use of urban network electricity and petrol oil for energy needs	Thermal energy is recovered by heat exchangers & heat pumps systems from the MBR effluent	TRL 4 → 6	10 kW	Thermal energy recovered and used to cover technology processes as well as thermal need of the nursey (e.g. buildings, greenhouses)	The design of the energy recovery system has finished and the construction of this element is expected to start soon.

4. Summary Table: material

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 8 Athens (EL) Location: Urban tree nursery in the Goudi Park	Sub-Task 1.4.10 Nutrient recovery for urban agriculture	Use of commercial fertilizers	Compost-based eco-engineered growing media products	TRL 4 → 6	100 kg/w	Compost obtained from organic materials of pruning waste and thickened wastewater sludge used as on site as fertilizer	The rapid composting bioreactor (RCB) for producing on-site fertilizer has been constructed and has been delivered in the site. The installation and connection with the other elements is pending.

5. NextGen solutions

- Chemitec, EYDAP, NTUA
- CoA, Biopolus
- Biopolus, CoA, NTUA
- Biopolus, NTUA

5.1 Flow scheme of the water and material recovery

5.2 UWOT model for the water cycle (→ WP2)

5.3 Pictures of the sewer mining unit

Sewer Mining unit: MBR technology consists of a hybrid unit UF and a biological unit. All construction works have been completed and the unit has been installed in the Nursery. In addition, the UV disinfection unit has been installed. Finally, tests have been performed with clean water.

5.4 Sewage tank & pumping station

Sewage tank: The sewage collection tank has been installed for treatment after the necessary excavation activities.

Pumping station: The pumping station has been constructed and installed on site after excavation works. In addition, all the necessary operation tests of the pumping station have been carried out.

5.5 First tests of the configuration operation with clean water

More videos and photos will be included after first tests

5.6 Rapid Composting Bioreactor for material recovery

Material recovery & fertilizer production system:

The construction of the Rapid Composting Bioreactor system has been completed. The process is carried out by mixing thickened sludge and treated pruning. The installation and connection of the system with the rest of the pilot device is pending.

Reactor size D=1,2 m, H=1,8 m, V=2 m³

Procedure

5.7 P&I diagram of energy recovery unit

Energy recovery system: The technical parameters of the wastewater heat recovery system using heat exchangers and heat pumps have been finalized; the construction and installation of the system is pending.

Completion of energy recovery unit study and P&ID

6. Operational procedures and methodologies: water

During the pilot operation, the quality and quantity of regenerated water is monitored according to the specific requirements in order to ensure the water quality just before the irrigation of the Nursery plants.

Water	Water yield of the system (flowrate)
	Water quality (COD, BOD5, pH, CE, TSS, Turbidity, Total N, N-NH4+, Total P, E.coli, Total Coliform, Faecal Coliform)
	Energy consumption (MBR, Disinfection treatment)
	Reagents & materials required (nutrients, antiscaling agents, disinfection agents)
	Waste produced (sludge produced, membranes)

6. Operational procedures and methodologies: energy & material

The parameters of energy and material recovery procedures are monitored according to the specific requirements in order to ensure the energy needs and the quality standards of the compost product.

Energy	Wastewater in the sewer (flowrate)
	Wastewater temperature
	Wastewater in contact with heat exchanger (flowrate)
	Energy abstracted from wastewater (heat)
	Heat Pump power input (work)
	Coefficient of Performance (COP) for heating
	Temperature increase of supply side
	Flow rate demand side
	Energy supplied to demand side (heat delivered)

	Flow rates	organic C-, N- & P- concentrations & TS and VS contents
Material	Wastewater in the sewer	
	Processed wastewater of the sewer mining unit	
	Wastewater sludge to the mixing unit	
	Wood & green pretreated waste to mixing unit	
	Compost (material product)	

6. Operational procedures and methodologies: Tools (WP2)

In the frame of WP2, different tools will be applied at the case study in Athens:

- Quantitative microbial risk assessment via the AquaNES online tool
- Quantitative chemical risk assessment for the compost
- Life cycle assessment
- Life cycle costing
- Cost efficiency analysis
- UWOT: (re-)design and stress test of water supply

The results are elaborated in WP2 and will be presented in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3.

7. Results: status of the construction

Installation of industrial concrete base: The horizontal industrial concrete base is constructed to host the pilot configuration i.e. sewer mining unit, composting bioreactor, associated additional parts.

Power supply: The power needs of the site have been defined and power supply has been installed in the site.

Sewer Mining unit: The MBR technology constitutes of a hybrid UF and biology unit. The biology study has been performed and the construction of the unit was done accordingly. The SM unit is set on the site.

Pumping station: All the excavation works and set up of the equipment has finished. Testing of these elements have been performed.

Buffer tank: Excavation works have finished and the tank is set to be connected with the pumping station & the SM unit.

Material recovery system: The construction of the Rapid Composting Bioreactor system has been completed. The process is carried out by mixing thickened sludge and treated pruning. The installation and connection of the system with the rest of the pilot device is pending.

Energy recovery system: The technical parameters of the heat recovery system have been finalised in a technical description document.

7. Results: specific KPIs to be measured (actual vs expected)

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#8 Athens (EL)	Wastewater treatment and reuse	To produce regenerated water for irrigation of trees	Water yield of the system (produced/collected) [%]	To be tested	80%
		To reduce carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus content of the WW	BOD, COD, N, P: removal of each parameter vs inlet load [%]	To be tested	80%
		To reduce the TSS and turbidity of the treated wastewater	TSS and turbidity removal yield vs inlet load and inlet turbidity to the system [%]	To be tested	90%
		To reduce the pathogens content of the wastewater (system performance)	[E.coli] final effluent [CFU/100mL]	To be tested	90%
			[Total coliform] final effluent [CFU/100mL]	To be tested	90%
			[Faecal Coliform] final effluent [CFU/100mL]	To be tested	90%
	Energy	Recovery of thermal energy from the MBR effluent	Electricity consumption [kWh/m ³ regenerated water]	To be tested	3 kWh/m ³
	Materials	Production of compost for the recovery of nutrients	Nitrogen recovery rate [%] related to the wastewater sludge and the green waste	To be tested	65%
			Phosphorus recovery rate [%] related to the wastewater sludge and the green waste	To be tested	65%

8. Progress and next steps - water

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#2	<p>Athens, Greece</p> <p>Location: Urban Tree Nursery in the Goudi Park (Athens)</p> <p>Lead Partner: NTUA</p> <p>Partners involved: CHEM, EYDAP, CoA, BIOPOL</p>	Sub-Task 1.2.4	Sewer Mining Modular unit (MBR & UV disinfection)	A delay of installation of the pumping station has occurred also affecting the full operation of the wastewater treatment unit, but it is not expected to affect the initial plan of demonstration of the MBR technology. The pumping station was set in July 2020 and is currently tested for operation.	It is foreseen to shorten the time dedicated to evaluate the performance of the plant: 21 months instead of 24 months. So there is still enough time to properly evaluate the proposed technologies.

8. Progress and next steps - energy

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Delay	Contingency plan
#2	<p>Athens, Greece</p> <p>Location: Urban Tree Nursery in the Goudi Park (Athens)</p> <p>Lead Partner: NTUA</p> <p>Partners involved: CHEM, EYDAP, CoA, BIOPOL</p>	Sub-Task 1.3.4	Implement thermal energy recovery flexible solutions. Thermal energy is recovered by heat exchangers & heat pumps systems	The design of the energy recovery system has finished and the construction of this element is expected to start after the set-up of the composting bioreactor. The expected delivery date of the energy recovery system is December 2020.	It is foreseen to shorten the time dedicated to evaluate the performance of the heat recovery system: 18 months instead of 24 months. So there is still enough time to properly evaluate the proposed technology.

8. Progress and next steps - material

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Delay	Contingency plan
#2	<p>Athens, Greece</p> <p>Location: Urban Tree Nursery in the Goudi Park (Athens)</p> <p>Lead Partner: NTUA</p> <p>Partners involved: CHEM, EYDAP, CoA, BIOPOL</p>	Sub-Task 1.4.10	Compost-based eco-engineered growing media products	The rapid composting bioreactor for producing on-site fertilizer has been constructed and delivered in the site. The installation and connection of the unit with the other elements has delayed	It is foreseen to shorten the time dedicated to evaluate the performance of the composting system: 20 months instead of 24 months. So there is still enough time to properly evaluate the proposed technology.

8. Next steps planned: from November 2020 on

Task	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
Test and install filter bags for sludge thickening	█	█										
Test and optimize Sewer Mining unit	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Test small pumping station	█	█										
Perform testing for UV disinfection		█	█	█								
Install and test the rapid composting bioreactor unit		█	█	█	█	█	█	█				
Install and test the energy recovery elements (heat pump & heat exchanger)							█	█	█	█	█	█
Operation & testing of the full configuration									█	█	█	█
Optimization of the configuration										█	█	█

8. Progress

Planned timetable

Task description	Task	M1 - M6	M7 - M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Definition of water, energy and nutrient needs according to the existing needs of the Nursery.	1.2.4								
Design of the pilot wastewater reuse schemes to enable autonomous, decentralized resource recovery solutions.	1.3.4, 1.4.10								
Construction of a sewer mining unit, i.e. a mobile wastewater treatment unit in a container able to treat and provide reused water at the point of demand. The unit will be designed to cover existing water needs of the pilot area.	1.2.4								
Design, construction, testing and optimization of integrated energy and nutrient recovery technology.	1.3.4, 1.4.10								
Installation and testing of the sewer mining unit. Wastewater will be mined from existing sewers of EYDAP, treated and reused directly for urban green irrigation as well as for other non-potable uses (e.g. fire protection, washing of municipality vehicles), based on existing water needs of the Nursery.	1.2.4								
Operation of the sewer mining pilot, running of various scenarios and evaluation of performance.	1.2.4								
Installation and testing of a treatment unit for the reject flux of the sewer mining processes towards a twofold scheme: to produce energy (thermal energy) and nutrients (fertilizer) for the urban green, as part of a renewable energy and materials solution to support more complete autonomy of the configuration.	1.3.4								
Operation of the energy and nutrients recovery pilot, testing of various scenarios and evaluation of performance.	1.3.4								
Full operation and testing of the configuration for optimization purposes, in order to increase the acceptance of such CE approaches of water services.	1.2.4								
Assessment of results and extrapolation to other suitable demo sites.	1.2.4								

#9.

Filton Airfield (UK)

A former airfield in South Gloucestershire, north of Bristol

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Energy

Relevant data

Under construction: 144 ha
Value: Water circularity showcase

Relevant sectors

Urban services

Land developers

Commercial sector

Lead partners

YTL Developments
YTL GROUP

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/demonstration-cases/filton-airfield/>

The site was bought by YTL, a large Malaysian company with global operations, including Wessex Water in the UK and YTL Developments (UK) Ltd who are developing the site.

A masterplan has been approved, but further evolution of sustainable development ideas to implement is required.

The investment project (construction began 2018) includes a strategic Surface Water System (SSW), ensuring reliable drainage and allow local use of captured rainwater and water reuse.

1. General description of the site

Within the NextGen project, a circular economy concept in Filton Airfield is demonstrated through rainwater harvesting and wastewater reuse, low-grade heat recovery and nutrients recovery.

During the first year of the project, qualitative and quantitative assessment of rainwater harvesting in the Brabazon Hangars has been conducted using a water balance model. Along with that, in the second year of the project, a feasibility of heat and nutrients recovery from wastewater will be conducted through a simulation study.

In addition, there is a plan for a more densified residential zone (approx. 4600 units) that is awaiting approval and so this densified plan will be demonstrated within the NextGen context.

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Current situation

Filton Airfiled Master Plan

- Residential
- Green open space
- Mixed use (residential)
- Dual use
- Schools and nurseries
- Employment
- Mixed use (non-residential)
- Community
- Station
- Infrastructure
- Water features

YTL Developments
YTL GROUP

BRISTOL'S NEW NEIGHBOURHOOD

Brabazon

TO CITY CENTRE

8.8 MILES
15 MINS BY TRAIN
20 MINS DRIVE

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

- ✓ Integration of the drainage system into green infrastructure and urban reuse of water: rainfall and rainwater characterisation and its reuse

- ✓ Heat recovery from the sewer system and local use for heating

- ✓ Proposals of circular economy solutions to implement using NextGen insights and experiences

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Filton
Airfield

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 9 Filton Airfield Location: A former airfield in South Gloucestershire, north of Bristol	Sub-Task 1.2.7 Integrating alternative water sources at district level at Filton Airfield	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A former airfield in South Gloucestershire, north of Bristol, UK - YTL Developments will develop this former airfield into an attractive and sustainable area - YTL Developments have a densified plan (2700 → approx.. 4400) for residential area so this will be considered in the NextGen study. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralized solutions for increased circularity in new housing districts - The water, materials and energy circular solutions will be included in a masterplan for the site development 	TRL 7 → 9	600 m ³ storage capacity	Rainwater reuse for toilet flushing and Brabazon park irrigation	Ongoing
	Sub-Task 1.3.1 Local heat and energy recovery from wastewater			TRL 9	Waiting for final design	Domestic heating	Ongoing
	Sub-Task 1.4.9: Integrated recovery and use of nutrients at district level			TRL 9	Waiting for final design	On-site reuse	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Filton Airfield case (T1.4.9) has been slightly delayed in the material activities due to the contract agreement required between partners. - Start-up of a desk study on the materials recovery activities was foreseen on March 2020, but due to COVID-19, it has been delayed after November probably.

5. NextGen solutions

Filton Airfield Aerial View Video

5. NextGen solutions

Local recovery and reuse of water, energy and nutrients

1. Water: local use of rainwater

2. Energy: heat recovery from the sewer system & biogas use

3. Nutrients: resource recovery from wastewater & food waste reuse

6. Operational procedures: rainwater reuse

Quantity analysis - Optimal storage tank

Rainwater Harvesting System

YTL Arena Bristol

Rainfall

Harvesting

- Catchment area
- Runoff coefficient
- First flush
- Filter

Storage

- Rainwater tank

Distribution

- Pump station
- End-uses

Methodology

Historical rainfall data

- 1968-2018

Water balance model

- Yield after spillage (YAS)
- Mains water supply
- Toilet flushing and irrigation
- Water saving efficiency (WSE)

Economic analysis

- Cost savings (£)
- Unit water cost (£/m³)
- Sensitivity analysis (water tariffs, rainfall patterns, discount rates)

Tank sizing (m³)

6. Operational procedures: rainwater reuse

Quantity analysis - Optimal storage tank

Rainwater collection from the roof of the Brabazon Hangars

Rainwater reuse for toilet flushing and Brabazon park irrigation

6. Operational procedures: rainwater reuse

Quality – Fresh rainwater sampling point (SP)

Wind from SW (South Westerly)

6. Operational procedures: heat recovery potential

Sewer Network Information

SIMDEUM/SWMM

*SIMDEUM: SIMulation of water Demand, an End-Use Model

*SWMM: Storm Water Management Model

Water Demand Patterns & Temperature

Discharged Wastewater Flow & Temperature

Available Power

6. Operational procedures: nutrients recovery

6.1 Exploring eco-friendly sanitation systems: a desk screening

Eco-sanitation system options: waterless or composting toilets, vacuum toilets and urine-diverting toilets
→ Nutrients recovery (e.g. phosphorus, urea)

1

2

6. Operational procedures

Tools in WP2 to assess circular elements at Filton Airfield

- UWOT system design of water supply
- This information will be collected in D2.3

7. Specific KPIs (actual vs expected)

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Key Parameter Indicators (KPIs)	Current value	Expected value
#9 Filton Airfield (UK)		To increase urban reuse of water - quantity analysis	Volume of collected and stored water (m ³ /year)	NS	NS
			Volume of water recovered vs rainfall (m ³ /m ²)	NS	NS
	Water	To increase urban reuse of water - quality analysis	pH	7.0-8.2	6.5-8.4 ^b
			Conductivity [μS/cm]	8-50	<700 ^b
			BOD [mg/L]	<4	NS
			TDS [mg/L]	2.9-30	<450 ^b
			Turbidity [NTU]	<1	<5 ^a
			TN [mg/L]	<0.4	<5 ^b
			TP [mg/L]	-	<2 ^b
			E.Coli [CFU/100 ml]	<400	1000 ^c
			Legionella spp. [CFU/100 ml]	<10	NS
	Energy	To evaluate local heat availability	Energy recovery (kWh/m ³ produced)	NS	NS
Materials	To explore nutrient recovery options related to the wastewater sludge and to the food waste	Nutrient (N, P) recovery rate [%]	NS	NS	

^a Irrigation water quality standard: WHO (Salman, J., Abd-Al-Hussein, N., & Al-Hashimi, O. (2015). Assessment of water quality of Hilla River for Drinking water purpose by Canadian Index (CCME WQI). International Journal of Recent Scientific Research, 6(2), 2746-2749.)

^b Irrigation water quality standard: FAO (Abdollahi, Z., Kaviani, A., & Sadeghi, S. (2017). Spatio-temporal changes of water quality variables in a highly disturbed river.)

^c Irrigation water quality standard: Steenvoorden, J. (2007). Wastewater re-use and groundwater quality: Introduction. Water and Energy Abstracts, 17(2).

NS: not specified.

7. Results obtained

7.1 Rainfall data collected during the NextGen project

Period: 2019. September – 2020. July

- ✓ Rainfall trends in Filton seem to be similar with WS1 and WS2 → Historical data collected from both was used to conduct a rainwater harvesting preliminary feasibility study.

7. Results obtained

7.1 Rainwater reuse – Quantity Analysis

Historical rainfall trend 1968-2018

- ✓ The annual average rainy days is 128 days.
- ✓ Two years (2000 and 2012) received significant precipitation of 1112 and 1125 mm, respectively while in 1973 and 2010, the average annual rainfall was 569 and 584 mm, respectively.

7. Results obtained

7.1 Rainwater reuse – Quantity Analysis

Commercial Building

Rainwater Harvesting System

Methodology

Optimal Tank Size: 400-600 m³

- Three water demand scenarios; toilet flushing, irrigation and combined use
- The water saving efficiency of RWHS was correlated with water demand scenarios.
- Water tariffs and discount rates played a significant role in reducing the unit water cost of RWHS.
- Better hydraulic and economic performances were expected for RWHS with a tank between 400 and 600 m³.

7. Results obtained

7.1 Rainwater reuse – Quantity Analysis

Residential Building

Residential Type	Bedroom breakdown	Standard plan
Apartment	1	68
	2	68
Houses	2	36
	3	36
	4	35
Total		278

Supply

- Rainfall data
- Collecting surfaces & evaporation

Demand

- Population Density
- Household appliances

Urban Water Cycle Simulations

Water Balance Scenario

Phase 1 Location

7. Results obtained

7.1 Rainwater reuse – Quantity Analysis

Residential Building

Phase 1 Location

- ✓ The 2-, 3-, 4- and 5-bedroom housing units does collect enough rainfall to be able to meet the non-potable water demand.
- ✓ The **apartment** units are the only residential unit type which **does not collect** enough rainfall to be able to meet the non-potable water demand due to mainly the smaller collection surface.
- ✓ Further research is needed.

7. Results obtained

7.2 Low-grade energy recovery (ongoing)

Foul sewer network layout in EPA SWMM

Analysis of UK time use data to feed in to SIMDEUM probability functions

Dataset:

Gershuny, J., Sullivan, O. (2017). United Kingdom Time Use Survey, 2014-2015. Centre for Time Use Research, University of Oxford. [data collection]. UK Data Service. SN: 8128, <http://doi.org/10.5255/UKDA-SN-8128-1>

7. Results obtained

7.3 Nutrients recovery: Scenario study (ongoing)

- ✓ Determine the availability and feasibility of local fertilizer production and utilization from wastewater

Housing plan - Phase 1

Residential Type	Bedroom breakdown	Min. Occupancy	Max. Occupancy	Standard plan	Densified plan
Apartment	1	1	2	68	136
	2	2	4	68	136
Houses	2	2	3	36	36
	3	3	4	36	36
	4	4	5	35	35
	5	5	7	35	35
Total				278	414

Eco-houses

Human waste, kg/day

Waterless or Composting toilets

Food waste, kg/day

Home composting or Waste treatment facility

Water savings, L/day

Fertiliser, kg/day

8. Progress and next steps

# N°	Case Study	Involved sub-tasks	Baseline: CE intervention / demo type	Status	Contingency plan
#9	Filton Airfield, UK Location: A former airfield in South Gloucestershire, north of Bristol Lead Partner: YTL Partners involved: UBATH	Sub-Task 1.2.7	Integrated system of water recovery and reuse (rainwater recovery and reuse)	The data collection from the Filton Airfield site has been delayed due to travel bans. However, we are expecting the acceleration of the data collection after August probably.	This will have a marginal impact on project activities, however, due to covid-19 situation in the UK, YTL and UoB agreed to held the 2 nd CoP meeting in early 2021.
		Sub-Task 1.3.1	Low-grade heat recovery from sewer		
		Sub-Task 1.4.9	Material recovery: Possibilities of local recovery of nutrients from wastewater streams	Delay in exploring options for materials recovery and local reuse due to some delays to site construction and they do expect that YTL Developments will experience some delays to site construction and further development of a masterplan for the site development.	

8. Next steps planned: from November 2020 on

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Task description	Task	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40
Design an integrated system for rainwater collection, urban run-off and surface water management in the Filton Airfield Development, including a low-flow sewer network and water re-use options	1.2.7	Theoretical work											
Modeling and prediction of heat recovery and supply potential from wastewater in the Filton Airfield Development	1.3.1	Theoretical work											
Determine the mass balances (availability) and feasibility of local fertilizer production and utilization from wastewater and organic waste streams at the Filton Airfield Development	1.4.9	Theoretical work											
Implement, construct an integrated design for water, energy and nutrient recovery at a local scale in the Filton Airfield Development	1.2.7 1.3.1 1.4.9	Full-scale											

- The 2nd community of practice meeting: January 2021 (M31).

8. Next steps Updated timetable

Full-scale
Pilot-scale
Theoretical work

Task description	Task	2019		2020		2021		2022
		M7-M12	M13-M18	M19-M24	M25-M30	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-M48
Install rain gauges and determine the local water balances and water flows at the Filton Airfield Development	1.2.7							
Setup and conduct a monitoring plan for rain and run-off water quality	1.2.7							
Design an integrated system for rainwater collection, urban run-off and surface water management in the Filton Airfield Development, including a low-flow sewer network and water re-use options	1.2.7							
Modeling and prediction of heat recovery and supply potential from wastewater in the Filton Airfield Development	1.3.1							
Develop local system for local energy recovery from wastewater and food waste by small scale AD systems	1.3.1							
Determine the mass balances (availability) and feasibility of local fertilizer production and utilization from wastewater and organic waste streams at the Filton Airfield Development	1.4.9							
Design low-flow local wastewater and organic waste collection and transport system (low-flow sewer) that enhances processing for heat recovery, energy production and nutrient recovery	1.4.9							
Implement, construct an integrated design for water, energy and nutrient recovery at a local scale in the Filton Airfield Development	1.2.7 1.3.1 1.4.9							
Demonstrate and monitor integrated water, energy and nutrient factory at the Filton Airfield Development	1.2.7 1.3.1 1.4.9							

#10. Timișoara (RO)

Design parameters for the Timisoara WWTP:

- The WWTP treats sewage for about 0.44 million PE;
- Average daily flow rate = 2,400 l/s;
- Maximum daily flow rate = 3,000 l/s;
- Annual sludge production = 38,000 m³/year;
- BOD = 22,000 kg/day;
- Suspended solids = 28,000 kg/day;
- Ammonia = 5.400 kg/day;
- Phosphates = 1.600 kg/day.

Introduction to the demo case:

<https://nextgenwater.eu/demonstration-cases/timisoara/>

Towards a next generation of water systems and services for the circular economy

Circular solutions for

Water

Materials

Energy

Relevant data

Agriculture

Water

Industry

treatment

Lead partners

Business Development Group

1. General description of the Timisoara WWTP

- **The dimensioning** of the Timisoara WWTP is based on the design flow to treatment of 3 m³/s. The design flow is determined 25% higher than the estimated average flow of 2.400 l/s.
- Thus the maximum flow to screenings is hydraulically limited to 4.3 m³/s by the new constructed “Water Brake”.
- When the sewage stream exceeds the designed capacity limit, the excess is taken by four first flush storage tanks. When this limit is also exceeded, the stream is screened by an automated cleaned rack and then pumped into the Bega river, by seven Flygt pumps, at a rate of 3,500 l/s.

- **The entire treatment** process consists of three subsystems comprising the unit operations: Mechanical Treatment, Biological Treatment, Sludge Treatment.
- The biological treatment phase includes the nitrification-denitrification process and the chemical treatment for the removal of phosphor.
- The removal of phosphor is achieved by chemical treatment, using the ferrous sulphate as coagulation agent and a dosing and injection system.

- The biomass is separated in eight secondary circular settlers, with diameters of 40-48 m.
- The excess sludge is stored in tanks, thickened and dewatered with polyelectrolytes.
- The plant is equipped with a dosing system for the polyelectrolyte and the sludge is dewatered and thickened to approximately 20-22% DS on three Bellmer filters.
- After solar drying the stabilized sludge is disposed to a landfill.

2. State of play at the start of NextGen

Flow Management Diagram

Flow Chart of Extended aeration Activated Sludge Process

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

- **To demonstrate sludge management with production of by-products and energy**, by pilot-scale testing of thermochemical conversion of sludge producing different output (biochar, oil and gas), which can be exploited energetically as fuel or soil enhancing agent or sorbent.

- **To perform a feasibility study of water reuse of effluent** from the Timisoara WWTP for urban, industrial and agricultural applications. This includes a potential analysis of water reuse options and a feasibility study for identified users in the Timisoara region.

- **To promote regional partnership** with industrial and agricultural stakeholders for wastewater reuse after treatment.

3. Objectives of the NextGen solutions

Positioning of demo case within the CE

Technology Evidence Base (TEB).
Initial draft – to be finalised in D1.6

Timișoara

4. Summary Table

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	TRL	Capacity	Quantifiable target	Status / progress
# 10 Timișoara (RO) Timiș County (Romania)	Sub-Task 1.2.5 (Water)	No previous study	Feasibility study on reclaimed water production possibility and regional demand	Theoretical work		Regenerated water for several uses (industrial, urban and agricultural uses)	Started, progress as planned
	Sub-Task 1.4.6 (Energy)	Currently there is no energy production at the WWTP.	Estimate potential production of energy by thermochemical conversion of sludge into several by-products.	Pilot scale (TRL = 4)	2.6 kWh/kg sludge DS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of energy (kWh) produced from sludge (kg). 	The subtask has not started yet but we can hope to start it by the end of this year depending on the pandemic situation.
	Sub-Task 1.4.6 (Material)	No useful by products are being produced at the WWTP	Production of by-products by pilot-scale testing of thermochemical conversion of sludge	Pilot scale (TRL = 4)	2 kg/h	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amount of by-products (biochar) obtained from sludge (kg). Quality of biochar and oil and gas produced 	The subtask has not started yet but we can hope to start it by the end of this year depending on the pandemic situation.

5. NextGen solutions

Scheme of the new Nextgen solution

Pilot equipment (Thermo-Catalytic Reforming). Produce GAC from sewerage sludge

Part of process scheme

G : granules
GAC: granulated activated carbon
..... undefined processes

5. New NextGen solutions

Principal and main characteristics of the pilot plant

The pilot plant (located within a sea container of 20 feet (6.05m)) is fed with min. 80% DS sludge from the Timisoara WWTP. Possibilities to characterize GAC by different analytic parameters according Henning&Kienle(2010)

GAC-Adsorber:

- Empty Bed Contact Time: residence time by EBCT [min] and normalized volumes in flowed bed volumes (BV)
- Wastewater matrix characteristic: DOC concentration in adsorber inflow C_0 , DOC [mg/l], normalized Concentration C/C_0
- Concentration of micro-pollutants in adsorber inflow/outflow by 12 priority substances according to UVEK

Chemical and physicochemical tests with produced GAC

- Adsorption capacity by methylene blue titer, Iodine number, Phenol, UV-Adsorption or TOC
- Structure Analytics e.g. surface area, pore size distribution, pore volume by BET-, Dubinin-or Freundlich-Isotherms
- Surface Structure by SEM (scanning electron microscope) and EDX (energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy)
- Moisture content, ash content, volatile matter by TGA, surface charge by zeta potential
- Functional groups on surface by FTIR analytics

Mechanical Tests with produced GAC:

- Bulk-and tap density, absolute or helium density
- Mechanical strength: abrasion strength, impact hardness, ball-mill hardness, stirring abrasion, ro-tap abrasion
- Grain size distribution

5. New NextGen solutions

P&I diagram of the pilot plant

5. New NextGen solutions

Pictures and/or videos of the pilot plant

Thermo-Catalytic Reforming

1. Pilot equipment – technical specifications

Pyrolyseofen TCR®-2
Plant capacity: 2 kg/h
Volume storage: 25 L
Temperature: 200 – 650°C
Inertgas: Nitrogen N₂

5. Scientific questions

- Which pyrolysis parameters, e.g. temperature, residence time and heating rate, lead with dried sewage sludge and biomass to an optimal carbonization in terms of coal yield, inner surface and on the pore size distribution?
- Which methods of chemical activation are best suited for sewage sludge pyrolysis with regard to their adsorption properties? In particular regarding their adsorption capacity, the internal surface, the stability of the granules and their pore size distribution in order to achieve optimal retention of micro-pollutants in wastewater.
- Which parameters e.g. adsorption capacity, porosity, pH and surface charge, are decisive in sewage sludge and biomass pyrolysis in order to achieve the formation of an efficient biofilm on GAC in context of bacteriological activated carbon?

6. Operational procedures

A pyrolysis pilot plant will be installed to produce biochar, gas or oil from sewage sludge .

We will test the options to assess substrate suitability and best yields depending on C-content of sludge.

Product characterisation and options for use of the products will be tested, *i.e.*, biochar for soil enhancement in agriculture, landscaping or other technical applications, and gas/oil use in biofuels for vehicles.

The yield and quality of the recovered products will be assessed, as well as the market potential and suitable cost recovery schemes for the use of these products. An energy assessment (kWh/kg product) will be performed as well.

7. Results and specific KPIs of the NextGen solution (actual vs expected)

Case study	Topic	Objectives	Specific Key Performance Indicator (KPI)	Current value	Expected value
#10 Timisoara)	Wastewater treatment and reuse	Theoretical study	Feasibility study	0 %	100 %
	Energy	WWTP sludge processing by pyrolysis	Quantity of processed sludge having at least 80% SU	0kg	600kg
	Materials	Evaluation of the viability of the pyrolysis by products	Obtaining a quantity of biochar of 20% of kg DS	0%	100%
			Obtaining an amount of oil of 5% from kg DS	0%	100%
			Obtaining a quantity of synthesis gas of 5% from kg DS	0%	100%

8. Progress and next steps planned

Case Study number & name	Subtasks	Technology baseline	NextGen intervention in circular economy for water sector	Status	Contingency plan
# 10 Timișoara (RO) Location: Timiș County (Western Romania).	Sub-Task 1.2.5 (Water)	No previous study	Feasibility study on reclaimed water production possibility and regional demand	No deviation	None
	Sub-Task 1.4.6 (Energy)	Currently there is no energy production at the WWTP.	Estimate potential production of energy by thermochemical conversion of sludge into several by-products.	No deviation	None
	Sub-Task 1.4.6 (Material)	No useful by products are being produced at the WWTP	Production of by-products by pilot-scale testing of thermochemical conversion of sludge	No deviation	None

8. Progress and next steps planned

Next steps

Task description	Task	M31-M36	M37-M42	M43-48
Description of water balance and identification of potential applications in close-by users (water quantities and qualities).	1.2.5			
Field study for sludge thermal treatment for biochar and biogas production.	1.4.6			

Conclusions

D.1.2. aims to demonstrate the operational status of the Nextgen demo cases in M30 of the project. The presented report underlines the potential of the NextGen solutions implemented for water reuse, nutrient and energy recovery in the 10 demo cases, demonstrating the on-going activities and providing the first technical results of the 10 case studies.

Pictures of installed and running prototypes and pilot plants are provided. A first round of KPIs and technical results are also presented in D.1.2, with a detailed plan of next steps per each site. Even though, final KPI results demonstrating the benefits of NEXTGEN CE solutions are expected by the end of 2021 and will be included in the final deliverables of WP1 (D.1.3, D.1.4 and D.1.5).

All sites have started their demonstration activities and have shown their operability in M30, with the exception of the demo case of Timisoara (RO) which was incorporated in M19 replacing Bucharest. For Timisoara case, a detailed next step plan is provided and, although the activities are just starting, it is expected to be fully operational in the following months.

nextGen

Circular Water Solutions

D1.2
Operational demo cases

EURECAT

KWB

University of Bath

MATERIALS

ENERGY

WATER

The consortium has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 776541.

FOLLOW US

